

OPENING BIG DATA FOR A SUSTAINABLE FUTURE

Review of the CASEarth
Program's Data Policy

A wide-angle landscape photograph showing rolling green hills and mountains under a clear sky. The foreground is dominated by dark green, grassy slopes. In the middle ground, there are more rolling hills and a valley. In the background, a range of mountains with some snow-capped peaks is visible under a bright sky. A body of water is visible at the bottom of the frame.

FULL REPORT

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This independent report was requested from CODATA by the CASEarth Program, and specifically the CASEarth Review Team, who comprise the primary intended audience. Nevertheless, we hope that government decision-makers with an interest in Open Science and data infrastructures, members of the research and policy communities concerned with Earth observation data and the SDGs, as well as data policy experts may find the analysis of interest.

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

*Antarctic Expedition
by CASEarth*

I INTRODUCTION

The Chinese Academy of Sciences Big Earth Data Science Engineering Program (CASEarth) is a well-structured, well-funded research activity that is perhaps the most prominent research program now at CAS. By revising its focus to the United Nations Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) during the course of this review, the Program has sought to achieve global international prominence and relevance that will carry it forward through the International Research Center of Big Data for Sustainable Development Goals, or CBAS. It therefore promises to assume a leadership role in Chinese and international research on the SDGs using Big data.

A major part of that leadership and prominence can be

attributed to the CASEarth Program's open data policy and the free, online availability of many of its data holdings. These networked data have both classic public-good characteristics and support the highly important public-interest objectives that are embodied in the SDGs themselves, particularly for the Low-to-Middle-Income Countries (LMICs).

This review report is intended to strengthen the CASEarth Data Policy and, accordingly, the impact of the Program for the SDGs, the international research community, and CAS itself. It is our hope that the suggestions presented here will help improve the Program to achieve its desired full potential.

II STATEMENT OF TASK

The CASEarth Program commissioned the Committee on Data, or CODATA (see: <https://codata.org/>) of the International Science Council to review the data policy regarding the Program's research data. Information about the CODATA Consultant Review Team and the CASEarth Review Team that managed the review process is provided in Annex 5.1 of this report. The Statement of Task given by the CASEarth to CODATA specified the following objectives:

- a. Define and describe key terms used in the CASEarth Programme and internationally that are relevant to data policy and this review
- b. Describe and assess the CASEarth Programme's Data Policy, particularly in relation to:
 - i. the status and framework of other relevant international good practices,
 - ii. the implementation of the Programme's initial goals,
 - iii. the development of new data sharing approaches and,

- iv. increasing the value of the data within its purview.
- c. Appraise the extent to which the CASEarth Programme's mission of supporting scientific contributions to the SDGs through earth observations has been facilitated by its data policy and the supporting human and technical infrastructures. The review will consider whether the data policy enables activities such as education and training, data science and applications, the development of various science-ready open data products, and other scientific and social objectives.
- d. Develop conclusions and propose formative recommendations.

This task statement guided our work and each chapter or section of the report addresses a specific aspect. The review process and methodology—comprising a literature review, interviews, and consultations with CASEarth personnel—are described in Section 1.2.

III SUMMARY OF CONCLUSIONS

The Chinese Academy of Sciences and the CASEarth Program consider the Program to be not only a “flagship” research initiative but are intent on establishing a successful open data policy based on generally accepted international norms. While the current policy provides a strong foundation, there are nonetheless improvements to it that can and should be made.

Since a data policy that is as open as possible and as closed as necessary is increasingly the norm in public international research, it is important to educate data users on the rationale underlying the FAIR (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable) Data Principles and the benefits that such a policy and adherence to it can bring. Conversely, it is essential to minimize the negative aspects of non-compliance in a realistic and useful manner.

The CASEarth platform now provides open access to rich varieties of data covering a wide range of fields and disciplines, including climate change, natural resources management, environmental conservation, and biodiversity and ecosystem studies. Not limited to scientific data sharing, CASEarth also allows the sharing of new algorithms and research models, with the ambitious goal of facilitating more complex cloud computing and online data analysis. Further improvement is needed to comply with the FAIR Data Principles, especially the interoperability and reusability principles, to facilitate access to and reuse of CASEarth datasets and data products by internal and external users.

There are many institutions worldwide engaged in Earth science research. Nevertheless, the CASEarth subject-matter focus is appropriate and well targeted, particularly regarding the emphasis on the UN's Sustainable Development Goals from a Big Earth and environmental data perspective, and will become even more so in the next phase of the Program. This is an area of critical importance in which few players are involved from a Big data standpoint. There also is room for improvement in the greater coordination of research objectives and data activities with other relevant groups in order to take advantage of synergies, minimize redundancies, and maximize the utilization of CASEarth

data—a key outcome of an effective data policy.

Compared with some conventional platforms run by foreign entities, this new platform in China stands out as the first to target the SDGs with some unique datasets and advanced algorithms to support decision-making in sustainable development. Domestically, the Program has received increasing support after China reaffirmed its commitment to the SDGs. Internationally, CASEarth not only benefits from China's Belt and Road Initiative through strengthened local collaborations, but also holds the potential to provide Big data support to developing countries.

Due to its relatively short history, CASEarth's methods of collecting, storing, sharing, and processing data will need continuous improvement even beyond the completion of the current Program. Building up data standardization systems for non-satellite data remains a complex problem that requires innovative solutions. Improved data categorization and data recommendation systems are necessary to ensure that the data can be quickly found by its potential users.

Good communication between engineers/technicians and scientists is crucial to identify further potential applications of data resources, enriching metadata with more accurate attributes, adjusting data formats and grid sizes, and enhancing the interoperability between satellite and non-satellite data. More effort is required to improve the English version of the data platform and the data products to allow foreign users to find, access, and reuse these data.

From the individual user perspective, foreign interviewees who worked with Chinese collaborators were generally very positive in their comments and impressions of CASEarth and the Chinese data resources they were using. It was not always clear, however, whether the data sets being referenced had been obtained directly through the CASEarth platform or through direct collaborations with Chinese colleagues. Many of the non-Chinese interviewees were either aware of CASEarth but had never tried to access its data resources or were unaware of the capacity that exists through CASEarth.

*Glimmer Satellite
Image of Beijing by
CASEarth*

Among both groups, there was limited knowledge of the CASEarth Data Policy. Any familiarity was often only the result of the CODATA Consultant Review Team having provided a translation of the policy prior to the interview. There were numerous calls for more active communication and dissemination on the part of CASEarth, especially in terms of making the data policy and other resources available in English, and for CASEarth to make a greater effort to raise its visibility in the international community. At the same time, CASEarth received high praise for its efforts and intention to make its data products open and accessible, even among those who were unfamiliar with CASEarth's capabilities.

Finally, the short courses for selected young researchers from LMICs, as well as online training modules, are primarily or exclusively focused on the scientific and technical aspects of research data and their use. The underlying rationale for a policy that emphasizes the FAIR Data Principles and the sharing and reuse of scientific data as much as possible is not being promoted systematically. While researchers do not need to be data policy experts, they should understand that rationale and approach to be successful in their work, particularly in furthering the goals of the CASEarth Program, the SDGs, and generally being good citizens.

IV SUMMARY OF RECOMMENDATIONS

The recommendations below are all directed to the CASEarth Program managers to decide how best to implement them, unless more specific actors are named. Also, the time for implementation is noted either in the near term, which means as soon as practicable but not later than the end of the current CASEarth Program, or in the longer term, for CBAS, which will take over the infrastructure and continue to provide

data services of CASEarth after its completion. The recommendations focus on both the CASEarth Data Policy and some programmatic aspects of the Program, as they are inextricably linked. Further development and implementation of the data policy and improvements in particular program elements are necessary to ensure its successful implementation.

*Destroyed land,
Poland by Curioso
Photography on
Unsplash*

IV.A. RECOMMENDATIONS TO IMPROVE THE IMPLEMENTATION AND EFFECTIVENESS OF THE CASEARTH PROGRAM'S RESEARCH DATA POLICIES

1. Based on the rationale presented throughout this study, we commend the CASEarth Program for adopting a default rule of openness for its data resources, subject only to legitimate and justified restrictions. The data policy should take advantage of and accentuate the positive underlying rationale and minimize the negative effects it might have. The areas that ought to be considered in developing the policy further are multidimensional, as outlined throughout this report, and should be reviewed internally periodically.

The CASEarth Program's Data Policy should encompass not only the open use of data and data products available through the Data Sharing and Service Portal (and its CBAS-based successor), but also the open aspects of data collection/submission, data analysis, and data processing by data owners and users outside of the CASEarth Program.

In addition, the CASEarth Program should work with other research projects and organizations across the Chinese government to standardize open data policies.
2. The CASEarth Program needs to publish its data policy (not just its data license) on its website, in both the Chinese and English versions, in order to promote visibility, transparency, and compliance.
3. Any changes made in the existing data policy need to be fully substantiated and justified so that there will be understanding and respect by those who need to subsequently implement and abide by it. Such changes should be made with the data user perspectives in mind.

Although there are some examples and anecdotal information that support the existing data policy, the CASEarth Program may wish to undertake several pilot projects to demonstrate to the public, policymakers, and funders the effects of an open and FAIR data policy. In this regard, CASEarth should analyze various "use cases" both inside and outside China in order to improve its data sharing policy, including its privacy protections.
4. Because "ownership" of the data policy is important to improve its effectiveness and subsequent compliance, key representatives of major stakeholder groups should be involved in the continuing development and implementation of the CASEarth Program's data policy.
5. Promoting compliance with the data policy should include a mix of incentives and penalties that are specifically targeted at the category of data providers and users in question.
6. In order to positively promote the data policy and its benefits, a selection of prizes and professional recognition should be implemented that each year reward the individuals, both within and external to China, who demonstrate the most creativity and productivity in using and disseminating the CASEarth Program's data for research and public interest uses.
7. The researcher or educator from outside of the government and business who uses any civil government Earth observation data, including CASEarth Program data, in a publication should deposit the data that underpin the results of the research in an open, public repository that is approved by CASEarth/CBAS or, at a minimum, make such data available upon request after publication or within a specified period. To help enforce compliance with this recommendation, the researcher or educator must demonstrate that the supporting data were made available.
8. We also commend the CASEarth Program for further focusing its research goals on the SDGs, thereby making the results of the research more socially and internationally useful and relevant. If the SDGs are extended beyond 2030, then CBAS should be extended as well.
9. Because environmental observational data increase in value the longer that they are collected, ideally in a consistent manner, they are useful for documenting long-term changes to the environment. The data collected under the Program's auspices therefore should not only be preserved, including sufficient backup, and continue to be made openly available as much as possible, but the research results, infrastructure, and data policy should be closely coordinated with and used as appropriate for any follow-on research to make sure that the investments in the existing CASEarth Program are fully utilized.
10. The CASEarth Program and its successor, the CBAS, should review its activities from a duplication of effort and coordination perspective on an annual basis, both in China and internationally.

IV.B. RECOMMENDATIONS TO ENSURE GREATER BENEFIT TO USERS OF CASEARTH DATA RESOURCES

1. The CASEarth Program should place more emphasis on providing data products, rather than raw data, that could support decision-making related to the UN SDGs. While we recognize that there exist different preferences among researchers, we believe that providing more data products concerned with the SDGs will help distinguish the CASEarth Data Sharing and Service Portal from other international data providers and increase the prominence of CASEarth and CBAS.

Further, the Program should continuously explore the potential broad value of its data products not only for academic communities but also for governmental and non-governmental institutions. It is essential for the Program to have some flagship data products that can support cutting-edge research and policymaking related to the SDGs.

2. The CASEarth Program should continue to improve the interoperability of its datasets, especially between satellite and non-satellite data. The Program ought to integrate data from multiple sources, rather than focusing only on remote sensing data with non-satellite data playing a complementary role.
3. Further enrichment and better scrutiny of metadata will be crucial to strengthen the reusability of the Big Earth Data. The CASEarth Program has devoted substantial effort to control data quality through external reviews. However, there are still concerns with inconsistent review standards. To make the data reusable, the metadata should be richly described with a plurality of accurate and relevant attributes. CASEarth also should develop more detailed and discipline-specific metadata specifications, including object description, date and time when the data was collected, and data collection method description, especially for raw data. Having a time stamp on data with the latest updated information also would be very useful.
4. The CASEarth Program should enhance the English version of the data sharing platform to strengthen the implementation and effectiveness of the Program's Data Policy. Limited English translation constrains the capacity of foreign users to find and access scientific data provided by the

CASEarth's Data Sharing and Service Portal. This situation directly impacts the ability of CASEarth to successfully implement its data policy, especially internationally. Increasing the number of data management scientists could be one solution to solve the communication problems. These would be professionals who can work as brokers between engineers/technicians building the portal and scientists from specific fields.

5. The CASEarth Program should continue to refine and improve the data access portal through additional actions, including: increasing the amount of data and information being made available; increasing the depth and breadth of data available in specific scientific areas; expanding the availability of data and data products relating to areas outside of China; and making the Data Sharing and Service Portal registration process as simple as possible.
6. Policymakers and funders need to ensure the long-term viability/sustainability of the CASEarth/CBAS and its data resources. The full value of the Program hinges on its sustainability.

Moreover, the continued success of the Program rests on the continued development of an open data culture in China. Improved incentive mechanisms are needed, including recording and publicizing data citations, carrying out periodical citation reviews, launching scientific data journals, and tracking the use of data products by policy and decision makers.

7. CASEarth managers need to address technical issues regarding CASEarth webpages and links between the CASEarth homepage and the Data Sharing and Service Portal, including: repairing broken links and fixing information on webpages displayed from dropdown menus.
8. CASEarth managers should increase the visibility and utilization of the CBAS/CASEarth Data Sharing and Service Portal (including cloud services) by: 1) participating in international symposia and conferences as attendees and presenters, and through sponsorship of display booths and other publicly accessible activities at appropriate meetings; and 2) increasing partnerships with international data organizations.

*Blue Ice in Antarctic
by CASEarth*

*Yili, Xinjiang,
China by CASEarth*

1 INTRODUCTION

1.1. BACKGROUND TO THIS REVIEW AND THE CASEARTH PROGRAM

In 2015, the United Nations General Assembly adopted Resolution A/RES/70/1, Transforming our world: the 2030 Agenda for Sustainable Development, which declared that “eradicating poverty in all of its forms and dimensions, including extreme poverty, is the greatest global challenge and an indispensable requirement for sustainable development.” The resolution identified 17 Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) based on the three pillars of sustainable development—economic, social, and environmental—and called for a “revitalized Global partnership” to ensure the achievement of those Goals.

The Chinese Academy of Sciences Big Earth Data Science Engineering Program (CASEarth) has committed to be a significant partner and contributor to the global effort to bring the power of Big Earth Data, particularly Earth observation and Earth science data, to the achievement of the Sustainable Development Goals. This Review of the CASEarth Program’s Data Policy is designed to ensure that CASEarth is maximizing its ability to generate data, information, and knowledge that will be readily available and useful to scientists and decision-makers striving to achieve the SDGs by 2030, both in China and across the globe.

Consistent with this vision of the importance of Big Earth Data and this review, the Big Earth Data Science Engineering Program, a Strategic Priority Research Program (Class A) of the Chinese Academy of Sciences (CAS), was officially launched in Beijing on February 12, 2018, with an initial implementation period of five years. The Program was founded as a major data infrastructure and research initiative that seeks to accelerate the use of various data resources of CAS, generally from remote sensing sources, to create scientific knowledge. A specific focus is on applications to address the Sustainable Development Goals and refining scientific knowledge in relation to the indicators of these goals.

The CASEarth Program has developed and implemented a data policy intended to be in line with good practice and with the Chinese State Council Decree on the Management of Research Data. (See Annex 5.3 for the Program’s Data Policy). The CASEarth Program’s Data Policy and management activities draw advantages from extensive resources of CAS and other units in China and abroad to create a data sharing platform to host Big data and cloud services, supporting data-intensive research and applications for a wide variety of fields. Its primary focus is fundamental and applied research through scientific programs, which are described on the CASEarth website (<http://english.casearth.com/>). The Program’s Data Policy is supported by various enabling practices, including the development of data curation tools and skills, an open data platform, and numerous science-ready open data products.

Following extensive discussions in the fall of 2020, the Chinese Academy of Sciences commissioned CODATA—the Committee on Data of the International Science Council (ISC)—in 2021 to review the CASEarth Program’s Data Policy. CODATA helps support and implement ISC’s mission of advancing science as a global public good by promoting global collaboration to advance “Open Science” and to improve the availability and usability of data for all areas of research.

CODATA has a longstanding history of work in the data policy arena, producing and contributing to reports and studies to advance Open and FAIR¹ data policies and practices. Most recently, the organization performed an independent 20-Year Review of GBIF, the Global Biodiversity Information Facility (CODATA 2020).

CODATA also has ties with the Chinese CODATA and CAS on bilateral and multilateral scientific data projects, including with the Aerospace Information Research Institute (AIRCAS) and its predecessor institutes. (See CODATA’s website at <http://www.codata.org> for more detail about CODATA’s background and activities.)

1 Wilkinson, M., Dumontier, M., Aalbersberg, I. et al. The FAIR Guiding Principles for scientific data management and stewardship. *Sci Data* 3, 160018 (2016). <https://doi.org/10.1038/sdata.2016.18>

1.2. THE REVIEW PROCESS AND METHODOLOGY

The Statement of Task given to CODATA by the CASEarth Review Team, which managed the review process, specified the following objectives:

- a. Define and describe key terms used in the CASEarth Programme and internationally that are relevant to data policy and this review
- b. Describe and assess the CASEarth Programme's Data Policy, particularly in relation to:
 - i. the status and framework of other relevant international good practices,
 - ii. the implementation of the Programme's initial goals,
 - iii. the development of new data sharing approaches and,
 - iv. increasing the value of the data within its purview.
- c. Appraise the extent to which the CASEarth Programme's mission of supporting scientific contributions to the SDGs through earth observations has been facilitated by its data policy and the supporting human and technical infrastructures. The review will consider whether the data policy enables activities such as education and training, data science and applications, the development of various science-ready open data products, and other scientific and social objectives?
- d. Develop conclusions and propose formative recommendations.

This task statement guided our work and was the basis for the contents of this report. At the beginning of each chapter, we identify the specific statement(s) of task that are addressed.

In conducting the review, the consultants engaged with and sought input from a range of relevant stakeholder groups, including but not necessarily limited to the organizations listed below. The experts interviewed were representative of the geographic regions served by the CASEarth Program, ensured a spread across the Earth sciences and SDGs, and were gender balanced. In many cases, the people interviewed for their perspective in one area also addressed one or more of the other categories of stakeholders. Those categories, which were developed jointly by the CASEarth Review Team and the CODATA Consultant Review Team, included:

- The CASEarth Program funder in China
- Earth sciences-related intergovernmental bodies
- Scientific bodies focused on Earth science and SDG areas
- Scientists of the CASEarth Program
- Data providers and managers
- Scientific publishers
- Researchers and other users (perspectives from Earth sciences and sustainable development fields)
- Earth science research data infrastructure bodies
- Technical data management experts
- Data policy makers
- Developers of CASEarth Platform (Projects 1-8)
- Developers of the Data Sharing System (Project 9: archiving, sharing, quality inspection, etc.)
- Developers of other similar platforms

The review began in February 2021 and concluded about 1.5 years later in September 2022. Because of the Covid virus pandemic, however, some of the original plans for travel and in-person meetings in Beijing were cancelled and held online instead.

The CODATA Consultant Review Team conducted 59 virtual interviews in China and in many other countries outside China. These oral interviews were augmented in some cases by written responses gathered from the interviewees. The experts who were interviewed thus reflected the broad diversity of the stakeholders and geographical regions. (See Figures 1 and 2 below, and Chapter 3 for more detail).

Figure 1. Geographic Distribution of CASEarth Data Policy Review Interviewees

Figure 2. Categories of CASEarth Data Policy Review Interviewees

The interviews followed a consistent format that focused on: (1) understanding the interviewee's relationship with and knowledge of the data in the CASEarth Program; (2) ascertaining CASEarth's Data Policy strengths, weaknesses, opportunities, and threats; (3) identifying issues relevant to the SDG and other uses of the CASEarth data; and (4) soliciting any other pertinent comments and suggestions. The interview questions and methodology

are described in Annex 5.4. The interviewees were highly engaged and many valued the contributions that CASEarth had made during its existence. They wished to provide input that would contribute to the future success of the Program. The detailed analysis for the interviews was given to the CASEarth Review Team; this report only provides high-level findings and the summary conclusions from the interviews.

1.3. STRUCTURE AND ORGANIZATION OF THE REPORT

The entire review report is summarized in a brief Executive Summary, which highlights the review process and the principal conclusions and recommendations.

The body of the report comprises a mix of descriptive, analytical, and advisory approaches consistent with the methodology described in the previous section. This chapter provides the descriptive background of the methodology, the particulars of the report, and the process of conducting the review. The description of the CASEarth Program, its data policy, the international dimensions, and the United Nations Sustainable Development Goals form the body of Chapter 2. That chapter provides a description and analysis of the sections b. and c. in the Statement of Task.

Select issues related to the CASEarth Program's Data Policy are addressed in Chapter 3, along with the high-level findings from the interviews of the CASEarth Program stakeholders both inside and outside of China, and continues to provide a response to the questions posed in the questions posed in b. and c. of the Statement of Task. The main conclusions and recommendations are presented in Chapter 4 and address all issues in the Statement of Task. Finally, the Annexes at the end of the report augment all the chapters in the report. In particular, Annex 5.5 on Conventions Used in this Report and Definitions of Key Terms covers question "a." in the Statement of Task.

*Bayinbuluke
Grassland, Xinjiang,
China by CASEarth*

*The United Nations
headquarters in
Geneva, Switzerland.
by Bernsten on
Shutterstock*

2 THE CASEARTH PROGRAM, DATA POLICY, AND THE PROGRAM'S RELATIONSHIP TO THE UNITED NATIONS SUSTAINABLE DEVELOPMENT GOALS²

2.1. BACKGROUND ON THE CASEARTH PROGRAM, ITS DATA SOURCES, AND PRIMARY RESEARCH PROJECTS

In this section, we provide a brief history of the CASEarth Program's formation and evolution, followed by a brief description of the Program's primary research projects and the data sources that they utilize.

The CASEarth Program officially began in February 2018, nominally for a 5-year period. (See: <http://english.casearth.com/>). However, the Program was preceded by extensive research activity at CAS in the Earth and environmental sciences and more recently by the Digital Belt and Road initiative, which is discussed in more detail later in this chapter. Moreover, the CASEarth Program will continue from 2023 under the new International Research Center of Big Data for Sustainable Development (CBAS), with many of the same features, experts, and information resources. It should thus be seen as a continuum of research, rather than as a one-time research program.

The CASEarth Review Team noted that the CASEarth Program was established as a key initiative of CAS and it is one of the largest in the Academy. Many of the Program's research findings are related to data or

data products acquired from previous and ongoing research projects. CASEarth produces a wide variety of data products through data reprocessing, analysis, and integration, leading to comprehensive scientific achievements. Moreover, as the CASEarth Review Team also stated, the data are thoroughly reviewed by experts before release, and all data and data products on the CASEarth data sharing platform are guaranteed to be of high value and quality.

In keeping with the continuum of research theme, the principal objective of the CASEarth Program now with regard to its data is to establish the next phase of research, which will be managed by CBAS. The Program is focused on achieving the following three overarching goals:

1. Produce and distribute massive amounts of multi-source data
2. Advance the exploration of novel research paradigms
3. Provide decision-making support capabilities with its data

2 This Chapter provides a description and analysis of b. and c. in the Statement of Task:

b. Describe and assess the CASEarth Programme's Data Policy, particularly in relation to:

- i. the status and framework of other relevant international good practices,
- ii. the implementation of the Programme's initial goals,
- iii. the development of new data sharing approaches and,
- iv. increasing the value of the data within its purview.

c. Appraise the extent to which the CASEarth Programme's mission of supporting scientific contributions to the SDGs through earth observations has been facilitated by its data policy and the supporting human and technical infrastructures. The review will consider whether the data policy enables activities such as education and training, data science and applications, the development of various science-ready open data products and other scientific and social objectives?

The Chapter that follows provides more detail and an evaluation of these issues, as do the Conclusions and Recommendations in the final Chapter.

PROMOTE KNOWLEDGE AND DATA DISSEMINATION

As discussed later in this chapter, the CASEarth Program has been dedicated to increasing the FAIR principles of scientific data, promoting data-driven research, generating new paradigms using cutting-edge technologies, and fostering global exchange as well as the use of research data.

The CASEarth Program has eight projects focusing on different fields as well as an administration project that manages all eight projects. It should be noted at the outset that Projects 1, 2, and 8 are either a satellite data source (Project 1) or technical data infrastructure (Projects 2 and 8). We do not analyze or review the technical aspects of the program because this review is principally about the CASEarth Data Policy. Moreover, of the five remaining research Projects, we accentuate Project 3, the Digital Belt and Road initiative (DBAR), which focuses mainly on the UN Sustainable Development Goals and is thus a precursor to CBAS. Nor do we separately address all of the research Projects, which are described on the CASEarth Program website at: http://english.casearth.com/index.php?option=com_content&view=article&id=69&Itemid=189. Finally, the CASEarth Administration Project examines the frontier exploration and management of these eight projects.

Also at the outset, it is essential to describe the sources of the data that are used in the research conducted in Projects 3-7 and that are managed by the infrastructures provided through Projects 2 and 8. We characterize the data sources broadly because the data used in the CASEarth Program's research are many and we do not have knowledge of them all. The Program's Data Policy applies to all the data provided by the Program, so the distinctions among the sources are not made because they are too voluminous and divergent.

The primary sources of data for the entire CASEarth Program are Earth and environmental remote sensing satellites. These include, but are not limited to, the Chinese holdings of foreign satellites and their sensors, such as the U.S. Landsat and the E.U. Sentinel series of satellites, and several other satellites operated by Chinese organizations. As the CASEarth Review Team pointed out to us, the CASEarth data sharing platform provides processed data products instead of the raw data of Landsat and Sentinel. According to NASA and ESA regulations, data sharing platforms are allowed to publish data products without requiring licenses.

Most recently, in November 2021, CAS, in close cooperation with CASEarth, launched its own satellite, the SDGSAT-1, in collaboration with several Chinese ministries. The CASEarth Review Team has indicated that they expect SDGSAT-1 to be the first in a series of remote sensing spacecraft that will provide data to the successor research programs of CASEarth at CAS and across China. The Big Earth data from remote sensing satellites that are made available by the CASEarth Program are augmented by other satellite data used by the 9 foreign International Centers of Excellence (ICoE)³ established by the DBAR Project 3 and by various air-based, ground-based, and sub-surface-based sensors and sensor systems.

Although Big Earth and environmental data are the main sources used by the CASEarth Program, there are also many smaller data sources that are provided or used by the affiliated researchers for different purposes. Such data sources are from individual investigators or small groups, or even citizen scientists, doing local research in areas such as biodiversity, environmental field work, ancillary social sciences, and are often combined with the Big data resources for all kinds of SDG applications.

Stakeholders interviewed from China pointed out that the CASEarth Program has one of the first platforms in China that provides open access to a rich variety of Earth science data covering a range of fields and disciplines. In addition, the utilization of satellite data from a variety of national and international sources allows for monitoring of ground surfaces at regular intervals, although application of these data may be limited by their spatial resolutions, repeat visit intervals, and other considerations. Further, the combination of satellite and non-satellite data allows scientists to utilize ground-based data to assess or validate the accuracy of the data, which in turn advances the science in various fields such as resources surveys, environmental management, and climate change mitigation.

Challenges do exist, however, in taking full advantage of these various capabilities as different types of satellite data are held by a number of ministries and institutions with different data sharing policies and platforms, as well as divergent interpretations of property rights and administrative frameworks, all of which can hamper data sharing across ministries.

3 The Digital Belt and Road International Centers of Excellence are located in: Bangkok, Thailand; El Jadida, Morocco; Lusaka, Zambia; Moscow, Russia; Helsinki, Finland; Columbia, South Carolina, USA; Potenza, Italy; Accra, Ghana; and Pakistan.

According to the CASEarth Review Team, the effectiveness of the data sharing platform can be evaluated by the following aspects, which the CASEarth Program uses:

1. The page views and data download volume of CASEarth data sharing platform;
2. Research outputs based on the data on this platform, such as the number of papers that have been published using the data;
3. The performance of data resource management and sharing services;
4. Infrastructure technology and service capacity to support the data sharing of CASEarth; and
5. Proficiency and professionalism of the CASEarth staff.

They also noted that the CASEarth Program does collect data and information about:

- Logs of visits and data downloads;
- CASEarth-supported research publications in recent years (see: <https://data.casearth.cn/en/paper>); and
- Factors indicative of data management and sharing capacities of CASEarth, such as: high download bandwidth, user-friendly technical support via phone or email, efficient data application process (usual approval time is within 3 business days), and ratings from users (on data products pages).

We now turn our attention to the international data law and policy background that helps to inform the CASEarth Program's Data Policy.

2.2. INTERNATIONAL LAWS AND POLICIES AFFECTING EARTH AND ENVIRONMENTAL RESEARCH DATA ACTIVITIES

2.2.1. Introduction

Data policy at the CASEarth Program institutional level, and more specifically, Earth and environmental research data policy, has several sources of law that control or affect different aspects of research data activities and are important to the context of this discussion. Although the Data Policy of the CASEarth Program is largely a self-contained institutional expression of the rules that govern its research data activities, it is important to establish the larger context within which it operates. Both international and China's research data rules derive from and are subject to governmental laws and policies and nongovernmental policies.

2.2.2. Laws and policy dimensions developed by governments

Public international law has a symbiotic relationship with national laws. On the one hand, it is informed by and arises from the laws of the nations that make up the world. It exists because nation states create it and agree to be bound by its provisions. It is limited largely, but not absolutely, by the sovereign status of each nation. On the other hand, international law is the mechanism by which relationships among governments and their subjects are ordered, and the rights and responsibilities expressed on an international basis. Such expressions of international law may be formal, as through treaties or agreements among the executive branches of governments or inferred more informally by the customary actions of nation states or the writings of experts and scholars. It is thus both a bottom-up and top-down mechanism.

There is a hierarchy of laws, agreements, and principles that inform the conduct of Earth and environmental observation activities, and especially the treatment of the data emerging from those systems. There are both those that restrict access to and the use of such data and those that promote it in specific circumstances.

At the highest level are treaties or conventions that are formal, multilateral agreements among many or almost all nations, such as the copyright treaties administered by the World Intellectual Property Organization (WIPO), a Specialized Agency of the United Nations. Those instruments have the greatest binding legal effect but are the most difficult to conclude. At the next level are executive agreements or intergovernmental Memoranda of Understanding (MOUs). Those are more specific to an issue or program and are also specific to the parties to the agreement. Next is customary international law as evidenced by the practice of states over time and governmental laws and policies at the national level. And finally, there are the writings and analyses of legal and other experts who form a consensus opinion about some issue or activity and that is supported by nongovernmental documents and actions. China participates in all of these levels of law, but there is no broad treaty specific to Earth or environmental data.

The legislation, regulations, and court cases at the national level are more directly relevant to all the activities of each country's citizens than international laws. This is certainly true in China and in all other

nations at a national, domestic level. The national laws and policies of other countries are also important in bilateral or broader cooperation that the CASEarth Program undertakes, including their enforcement, but that is beyond the scope of this review.

With regard to managing research data themselves, the grantmaking and contractual obligations of the national governmental research agencies in all countries are controlling or indicative of the restrictions or open provisions placed on the data collected or created by the researchers funded by those agencies. Similarly, governmental policy-making institutions affect how different aspects of research data activities are handled. Collectively and over time, the trends in the practices of all those entities, especially the largest or most influential ones, form a body of customary law and norms that may ultimately be codified. In the past two decades or so there has been a trend in those governmental agencies that fund research to make the underlying data more open, particularly after publication of the research results.

2.2.3. Non-governmental policies

Although international and national non-governmental policies have the lowest level of formal legal importance regarding the manner in which data are managed within the CASEarth Program, they do have the greatest significance to such activities from a normative and behavioral perspective. Because research data are not the subject matter of most international laws, except tangentially, the ways in which data are handled are informed principally by the writings and practices of the foreign and domestic non-governmental research community.

There are different categories of stakeholders that are relevant to this issue. This includes the data providers, data repositories, data platform operators, data managers, and data users, whether at the institutional, project group, or individual researcher level. In short,

these people may be researchers themselves, the technical and engineering professionals who provide the infrastructure for all phases of the data lifecycle, or the research funders. Universities are the main institutions that perform the scientific and technical research data work, but there are other, more focused organizations and research consortia that influence research data activities and policies, some of which are discussed further below. Also important are the scientific publishers of the research results, mostly in the form of peer-reviewed books and articles, but also on institutional websites and portals that often are not peer-reviewed. Many of the publishers are professional scientific societies, but also private-sector entities; research data sources may be corporate as well. An emerging network of data centers, often organized by (sub)disciplines, are important for making data available and reused, as are the more established libraries that are focused on research data and are frequently housed within major universities, ministries, or at CAS itself. Finally, there are emerging categories of stakeholders, such as citizen scientists, who contribute data to research institutions and programs.

These stakeholder categories coalesce and have greater policy impact in institutions and organizations, at both the national and international levels. Many of these organizations have issued data policy principles, declarations, and statements in the past two decades or so. Some of these groups are discussed in more detail in the next section, not only because they are important to the development and management of research data from the bottom up, but because the managers and experts of the CASEarth Program or CAS itself are active participants in some of these entities, or should be.

In addition to the policy impact of international organizations are the contracts and licenses that have been developed for the management of research data. The licenses that accompany research data and stipulate the respective rights of the data providers, managers, and users are explored more fully in the CASEarth Program context below.

2.3. INTERNATIONAL ORGANIZATIONS FOCUSED ON THE SHARING OF EARTH AND ENVIRONMENTAL DATA

As in the case of the international laws and policies, there are two kinds of international organizations that are central to the present discussion, intergovernmental and non-governmental organizations. Many of these groups are directly focused on the sharing of Earth and environmental research data internationally and many more at the level of each nation (but that we do not review) that also may be relevant to the CASEarth Program. In the case of the international ones, their activities may be further subdivided into those entities that are organized to make available the research data themselves, usually in a discipline-specific area, and those that formulate rules to guide research data activities. In what follows, we broadly characterize these two main types of international organizations.

2.3.1. Intergovernmental Organizations

There has been a great deal of attention in the past decade or so on access to and use of public sector information and government-funded data. There are many intergovernmental organizations that are directly relevant to promoting the sharing of observational Earth and environmental data and to developing principles and policies, both based on prior international law and in the formation of future law and policy, either international or national. There also are several such organizations that influence public-sector data laws and policies through the issuance of formal, peer-reviewed recommendations and principles.

We should note that we do not advocate that the CASEarth Program be directly represented in the membership of all these governmental organizations. In some cases, they already are engaged with them. In other cases, Chinese government ministries are the proper adhering bodies to such organizations. There also are too many with which to cooperate in a meaningful way. Any involvement of CASEarth, therefore, should be coordinated at the national level. However, the intergovernmental organizations that we do identify work in areas directly relevant to the CASEarth Program and, in many cases, form data policies and management techniques of which the staff of the Program at least

should be aware and monitor.

Because the focus of this review is on Earth and environmental observational data collected or made available by the CASEarth Program, these intergovernmental organizations and the principles they have formally issued are relevant in this context. We divide the intergovernmental organizations into two groupings, the United Nations and its Specialized Agencies and those outside the UN system.

Almost all of the UN's agencies have some bearing on the data policies and research data work of the CASEarth Program. Because a large portion of the CASEarth Program's international data activities is directed towards facilitating the monitoring and assessment of SDG indicators, the Program works closely with many UN organizations. According to the CASEarth Review Team, in most cases they utilize the Program's global data resources to provide final information and maps to many of the UN agencies. Indeed, over the course of the Program, CASEarth has had extensive and multi-dimensional relationships with the UN agencies and their engagement "has ranged from collaborations on important international publications, capacity development programs, to data support, data product development, and advisory roles in important committees and projects."⁴

Further, the CASEarth Review Team provided information that the CBAS, in cooperation with UN agencies, has already contributed significantly to key UN reports and global affairs. In particular, they reported that there was extensive cooperation with UN DESA, UNEP, UNCCD, UN-Habitat, UNBL, and FAO.

In addition to the UN agencies, there are several key intergovernmental organizations that should be noted. These are a few important examples, but this area should be systematically characterized and monitored for inputs and outputs of the CASEarth Program. The ones that we have identified include the Group on Earth Observations⁵, the Belmont Forum⁶, the Global Biodiversity Information Facility⁷, and the Committee on Earth Observation Satellites⁸.

4 Written communication from the CASEarth Review Team in February 2022, on file with the authors.

5 <https://earthobservations.org/index.php>

6 <https://www.belmontforum.org/>

7 <https://www.gbif.org/>

8 <https://ceos.org/>

2.3.2. Non-governmental international organizations

In addition to the intergovernmental organizations described above, there are many more non-governmental international organizations that play some role in shaping data policies in the Earth and environmental observation domain. In light of their non-governmental status, they only reflect the views of their members, so they are mostly bottom-up expressions of communities of practice rather than a consensus (or reflection) of the governments of nation states.

These organizations, involved directly in Earth and environmental observational research activities or in related data policy formation, exist in scientific and technical fields, the business community, and the data or informatics areas. We focus, first, on the non-governmental international entities that work on policy and management issues of research data. The other stakeholder types are discussed after that in the next section.

There are four primary organizations that focus directly on research data policy and management issues: the Committee on Data (CODATA) and the World Data System (WDS), both affiliated with the International Science Council, and the more recently formed Research Data Alliance (RDA) and the GO FAIR organization. Together, they have organized an informal group called “Data Together” (see <https://codata.org/initiatives/data-together/>) and hold a conference every two years referred to as the “International Data Week,” where issues of research data policy and management are explored. CAS and by extension, the CASEarth Program, have been actively involved in the first two of these bodies for many years and have monitored the developments of the other two in more recent years. Besides these four, the International Society of Digital Earth (ISDE), hosted by CAS, is very much involved in the CASEarth Program. Additional information about all five organizations may be found at: <https://www.codata.org>, <https://www.worlddatasystem.org>, <https://www.rd-alliance.org>, <https://www.go-fair.org>, and <http://www.digitalearth-isde.org>.

CODATA was commissioned to conduct this review of the CASEarth Program's Data Policy, as described in section 1.1. However, here we concentrate on the FAIR Data Principles and the CASEarth Program's implementation of them, since we specifically asked that question in our interviews.

The FAIR Data Principles recommend that all research data should be Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable, for both machines and people. The principles refer to three types of entities: data (or any digital object), metadata (information about that digital object), and infrastructure.

In our February 22, 2022 online discussion with the CASEarth Review Team, they noted that the FAIR Principles are well reflected in the CASEarth Program Data Policy. In 2019, the report on the Data Sharing Management Measures of the CASEarth Program was published, in which in item 15, chapter 4, it clearly addresses that CASEarth data should be open and shared with the users inside and outside the CAS according to the FAIR Data Principles. Specifically, the CASEarth Review Team communicated the following:

Findable: The CASEarth data should be uniquely and persistently identifiable by being assigned a globally unique and persistent identifier and the users can find the data easily with well described metadata, and (Meta) data should be registered and indexed in a searchable resource.

Accessible: The [access] conditions of the CASEarth data should be clear by giving a formal visiting address and access approaches. When the users find the required data, they can understand how the data can be accessed, including authentication and authorization, and the metadata should be accessible, even when the data are no longer available.

Interoperable: The CASEarth data should use a formal, accessible, shared, and broadly applicable language for knowledge representation, and include qualified references to other (meta)data. They can be easy to be integrated with other data and also can interoperate with applications or workflows for analysis, storage, and processing.

Reusable: The CASEarth metadata and data should be well-described so that they can be replicated and/or combined in different settings, being with a plurality of accurate and relevant attributes, released with a clear and accessible data usage license, with detailed provenance, and meeting domain-relevant community standards.

These four descriptions of the FAIR principles are excerpts quoted from the Data Sharing Management Measures, released internally in April 2019 on pages 6-7 and the CASEarth Technical White Book released internally in December 2019 on pages 27-30. As shown in the Data Sharing Management Measures, three elements (Findable, Accessible, Reusable) of FAIR are covered, elaborating on visions and strategies for data sharing at the initial phase of CASEarth Program. As CASEarth has grown, the 4th (and most challenging) element of FAIR—interoperability—was proposed in the CASEarth Technical White Book, which explicitly outlines the essential methods and techniques.

The FAIR Principles are reflected in the Data Sharing

License Agreement Section 3: Services:⁹ 1. (No. 1) You can freely register, browse, query, download and share data works and pages released by CASEarth related platforms; 2. (No. 4) CASEarth related data management and sharing platforms have provided CSTR, DOI, PID global unified identifiers for shared data across disciplines; and 3. (No. 5) You can freely register CASEarth related platforms, which will protect your information.

There is substantial additional information from the interviews which demonstrates how committed CASEarth is to adhering to the FAIR Data Principles. This is summarized in the next chapter.

2.3.3. Other Non-governmental IOs of Potential Relevance to the CASEarth Program

There also are many scientific organizations and programs that are affiliated with all or part of the CASEarth Program and its projects, frequently very specific to discrete research elements of the CASEarth Program. One such important organization is the [International Science Council \(ISC\)](#) in Paris, with which

CAS has been cooperating for several decades. Both CODATA and the World Data System are “affiliated bodies” created by the ISC, and the ISC has numerous activities germane to CASEarth research and its data policy as well. With regard to research, the ISC’s *Future Earth* Program (see: <https://futureearth.org>) is especially important, as is the *Open Data in a Big Data World* statement or “accord” (available at: <https://council.science/publications/open-data-in-a-big-data-world/>) as a guiding document for research data policy.

Moreover, the SDGs have their own organizations that work in their respective areas of focus. The CASEarth Program can benefit from forming relationships with many of those organizations, both as a way of getting information beneficial to its work and as a means of outreach and influencing the broader international community through the Program’s data and research results. As the CASEarth Review Team told us during the February 22, 2022 online workshop, the Program has developed collaborations with various international nongovernmental organizations, such as GEO, PEEEX, IUCN, ISDE, and some others to share expertise in Big Earth Data research and discoveries.

2.4. THE CASEARTH PROGRAM DATA POLICY

Chinese law and policy as they pertain to scientific data have evolved over time, but their evolution as a key focus in China has become much more pronounced in recent years. An excellent survey of national laws and policies in China is *A Review of Open Research Data Policies and Practices in China* (Zhang et al. 2020). We incorporate the results of that article by reference in this review report.

In particular, we are aware of bilateral cooperation on research data policy issues from 2000 to 2015 between the Chinese Academy of Sciences and the U.S. National Academy of Sciences (NAS), and more specifically between the Chinese and U.S. National Committees for CODATA under the auspices of those Academies, as well as through private practice from 2015 to the present. This time period, from 2000 to the present, maps well to the interest of CAS in data science and research data policy, generally, and in the role of Big data in the Earth and environmental sciences, specifically.

In the 2000-2015 period, there was an exchange of national delegations on these topics. The Ministry of Science and Technology in Beijing was especially active in the earlier 2000-2004 period and established the China Scientific Data Sharing Program and related data policy in 2003. A major workshop was held at CAS in Beijing in 2004 on these developments and a report documenting them, *Strategies for Preservation of and Open Access to Scientific Data in China*, was published (NAS 2006)¹⁰.

The Academies then formed a bilateral China-US Roundtable on Scientific Data Cooperation in 2006, which held six meetings between 2006 and 2012. Two of the four areas of discussion were in scientific data policy and in environmental and geospatial data. See <https://codata.org/china-us-roundtable-on-scientific-data-cooperation/> for a summary of those activities and results. All these activities directly influenced the current CASEarth Program’s open data policy.

9 <https://data.casearth.cn/en/statement>

10 See: <https://nap.nationalacademies.org/catalog/11710/strategies-for-preservation-of-and-open-access-to-scientific-data-in-china>.

Professor Huadong Guo, the director of CEODE and RADI, the founder of AIRCAS, and the Principal Investigator of the CASEarth Program, was also the President of CODATA between 2010 and 2014. In 2016, Professor Guo established the Digital Belt and Road international research program at CAS, which is focused on the use of Earth and environmental data for the UN SDGs. The CASEarth Program grew out of that initiative and was founded in 2018.

More recently, the State Council of China published the Notice of Scientific Data Management Measures on March 17, 2018 (see <http://lawinfochina.com/display.aspx?id=27873&lib=law>). Notably, that State Council Notice promoted the policy of “openness and sharing” of scientific data (Article 4). This law is particularly important to the CASEarth Data Policy and Licensing Agreement.

In September 2019, the China CODATA held a major international workshop on research data policy jointly with the international CODATA organization. That meeting produced a consensus CODATA Beijing Declaration, which presents 10 Principles and affirms the open data precepts and policies that guide the CASEarth Program's Data Policy as well. The Beijing Declaration is available at: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3552330>. In particular, it lists 55 previous open data policy documents from all over the world that form a very useful compendium of research data policies.

The CASEarth Data Policy builds upon and is consistent with the law and policy described above, both in China and internationally, and is influential as a written expression of data policy controlling the dissemination of environmental research data of the biggest current research program in CAS. Moreover, both the data policy

report and the Data Sharing Licensing Agreement on the CASEarth Program's website, which legally implements the data policy positions, are discussed further below. Because of their importance to this review, the main tenets of the data policy are reproduced in full in Annex 5.3, as is the link to the CASEarth Program's online Data Sharing Licensing Agreement.

Concerning the CASEarth Data Policy provided in Annex 5.3, several issues stand out. First, it emphasizes three main approaches:

- First, to ensure the continuous production and collection of high-quality data, principles and paradigms for data management and data sharing must be established, with special focuses on a data convergence mechanism and data sharing policies.
- Second, to provide long-term service of open data, supervision and assessment mechanisms must be established, with clearly defined evaluation systems and incentive programs.
- Third, it is necessary to consolidate the infrastructure of open data, enhance technologies and service capabilities, and build a professional team.

It then goes on to highlight five principles that need to be followed in implementing the data sharing systems of the CASEarth Program, namely, the principles of openness, consistent rights and responsibilities, usability, sustainability, and innovation-driven management.

These overarching principles are then followed by more specific implementation policies. We find these approaches and principles sound and appropriate for guiding the overall data policy. Table 1 is a summary of the basic principles of the CASEarth Data Policy.

Table 1. Basic principles of data opening and sharing of CASEarth

Basic principle	Details
1. Principle of opening	Except the data whose opening and sharing are limited or forbidden by particular national laws and regulations, scientific data produced from CASEarth should be opened and shared without preconditions. Anyone, any legal entity and institution cannot regard data as private resources.
2. Principle of unified responsibility, rights and interests	The responsibility, rights and interests of data supervisor, data users and data providers should be clarified to form the interest coordination mechanisms that promote data sharing and build the sound data sharing ecology. Data users should make the data reference clear while publishing the scientific research achievements, and data providers should guarantee the quality of data.
3. Principle of availability	Responsible units and persons of CASEarth, subjects and subsidiary subjects should collect and process all kinds of scientific data based on the requirements of one source for one datum, mark on each datum and dynamic updating. They also should establish and update metadata information on schedule to ensure the authenticity, accuracy and effectiveness of shared data. Besides, data's discoverability, accessibility, interoperability, reusability and quotability should be guaranteed.
4. Principle of sustainability	Long-term acquisition mechanisms of scientific data for CASEarth should be built to guarantee software and hardware facilities and special teams needed in management and operation of scientific data and develop technology supporting system of scientific data management, opening and sharing. The sustainability of scientific data opening and sharing for CASEarth should be ensured through continuous guidance of policies, promotion of incentive mechanisms and dual support of technology and facilities.
5. Principle of driving innovation	Big data has brought revolutionary change to the way of scientific research. The way of scientists to know the nature and acquire the scientific discovery has been developed from traditional observation stage, experiment stage and model stage into the current Big data scientific discovery stage. Scientific research innovation driven by Big data and scientific discovery can be continuously promoted through data opening and sharing.

Another very important expression of the data policy, which implements these policy principles in practice for the data users, is the Data Sharing License Agreement, which is available on the CASEarth website at: <https://data.casearth.cn/en/statement>. This document makes the platform and the data it contains very useful to researchers, particularly at the CASEarth Program, who have access to more data and services than researchers external to CAS. We cannot compare the CASEarth platform to others, whether within China or throughout

the world, since there are too many and the details too voluminous. Our general impression, however, is that the platform compares very favorably with other, similar open research platforms.

Moreover, according to a list of articles provided by Professor Dongmei Yan of the CASEarth Review Team, there are hundreds of high-quality publications sponsored by the XDA19 funds that used CASEarth data in the last 4 years, highlighting that CASEarth data

has contributed greatly to scientific research. These publications are increasingly co-authored with non-Chinese collaborators, growing from 13% of publications in 2018 to close to 20% in 2021, an important indicator of international recognition of both the availability and value of CASEarth's data resources. The 2018-2021 publication list is available at <https://data.casearth.cn/en/paper>.

Because open access to research data is not yet the norm in China, the CASEarth Program's data portal is thus a

pathfinding approach to Big Earth and environmental data in China. As such, its open data paradigm has the potential to change the culture of data management and use for research in China and in other LMICs, as well as to provide an example to other public research initiatives. However, while the open data policy aspects have been included in summer data management training programs for young Chinese and LMIC researchers, the CASEarth Review Team has reported that online courses do not have the open data policy element as part of the curriculum.

2.5. THE UNITED NATIONS SUSTAINABLE DEVELOPMENT GOALS AND THEIR RELATIONSHIP TO CASEARTH AND CBAS

The principal mechanism for organizing and managing the SDGs is the UN's Department of Economic and Social Affairs (UN DESA) and the CASEarth Program's research Project focused on the SDGs is the Digital Belt and Road (DBAR) initiative, which will continue under CBAS. Here we elaborate on the relationship between the United Nations and Chinese activities, beginning with a brief overview of the SDG Program at the UN, which is followed by an exploration of how the CASEarth Program and CBAS relate to the SDGs.

The United Nations General Assembly founded the SDG Program in 2015 as an outgrowth of the Millennium Development Program, which ended that year, and established the following 17 areas of focus or goals along with many sub-indicators:

- (1) No Poverty, (2) Zero Hunger, (3) Good Health and Well-being, (4) Quality Education, (5) Gender Equality, (6) Clean Water and Sanitation, (7) Affordable and Clean Energy, (8) Decent Work and Economic Growth, (9) Industry, Innovation and Infrastructure, (10) Reduced Inequality, (11) Sustainable Cities and Communities, (12) Responsible Consumption and Production, (13) Climate Action, (14) Life Below Water, (15) Life On Land, (16) Peace, Justice, and Strong Institutions, (17) Partnerships for the Goals

(See <https://sdgs.un.org> for more information).

The CASEarth Program's focus shifted to the SDGs in October 2019 and a new data classification system based on the SDGs was launched by CAS in March 2022. Because of the central orientation of CASEarth research to the SDGs, we explored in some detail the nature of that relationship in the interviews.

To start with, it should be noted that there are only a few international research initiatives that use Big Earth and environmental data to study SDGs and the CASEarth Program is certainly the largest. The UNEP report, *Measuring Progress, Environment and the SDGs*, cites the CASEarth Program's efforts as follows:

CASEarth has used Earth observations coupled with statistical analysis and modelling to generate data and estimates for three of the sub-indicators of 2.4.1 on sustainable agricultural practices (SDG 2 on zero hunger), SDG indicator 6.3.2 on water quality (SDG 6 on clean water and sanitation), SDG indicator 11.3.1 on land consumption rate (SDG 11 on sustainable cities and communities), SDG indicator 1.5.1/11.5.1/13.1.1 on human impact of disasters (SDG 1 on no poverty, SDGs 11 and 13 on climate action), and SDG indicator 15.3.1 on land degradation (SDG 15 on life on land).

As the CASEarth Review Team reported, working with UN DESA, the CASEarth Program is facilitating the mapping of existing available ocean databases at the global level to identify gaps and requirements of Low-to-Middle Income Countries (LMICs) in terms of data access, collection, and dissemination. The Program is also collaborating with UN DESA to design a toolkit and organize a capacity building workshop to enable data-driven decision making and monitoring of implementation of SDG-14.

In addition, the CASEarth Program provided input on data selection and analysis methods to the Good Practice Guidance for indicator 15.3.1 published by UNCCD. The CASEarth Program is currently working with UNCCD to conduct monitoring and scientific research at a global scale. They are also reportedly in extensive discussions about cooperating in data related services and SDG monitoring metrics with the UN Biodiversity Lab.

These and other examples show that there are substantial interactions between the CASEarth Program and the UN concerning the SDGs. The DBAR Project's ICoEs conduct further focused research in these areas, as detailed on the DBAR and ICoE websites. (See <http://dbeltroad.org/> and <http://dbeltroad.org/index.php?m=content&c=index&a=lists&catid=99>).

Foreign organizations have also requested the CASEarth Program to contribute its expertise and data resources to undertake case studies in monitoring progress in the SDGs in specific geographic and subject-matter areas. For example, CASEarth is closely collaborating with the National Research Council of Thailand to facilitate the monitoring of Thailand's national SDG progress. We should note as well that the DBAR External Evaluation Committee has prepared an External Evaluation Report of that Project, which is pending approval for release by the DBAR Scientific Committee (see DBAR External Evaluation Report, publication pending).

Finally, as noted earlier, the Chinese Academy of Sciences recently established The International Research Center of Big Data for Sustainable Development Goals (CBAS), which aims to harness Big Earth Data to serve the SDGs. The Center conducts multidisciplinary research related to Earth system science, social and economic sciences, and sustainability science. Specifically, the Center is devoted to the monitoring and evaluation of SDG indicators in the

areas where Big Earth Data plays a key role, including environmental commons, urban and peri-urban development, food security, and energy decarbonization.

CBAS aims to construct the theory, method, and technical system around Big data in support of the SDGs, establish an open and shared Digital Earth scientific platform, and lead the development of the Big data discipline for global sustainable development. The Center also plans to offer comprehensive data sharing, technical support and decision support services to relevant UN agencies, its member states and China, and become an international first-class comprehensive research organization.

The Center will be developing an SDG-relevant Big Earth data platform featuring high-performance computing, Big data analysis, AI, and iCloud service. The data-driven platform is equipped to receive, process, distribute, and share Big Earth Data, and will serve as a one-stop infrastructure addressing SDG indicator-related monitoring and evaluation.

The CBAS initiative thus will build upon the foundation established by the existing CASEarth Program. The lessons learned from the data sharing policies and practices developed and implemented during CASEarth's first five years of operation will be critical to the ultimate success of the CBAS initiative, particularly with regard to research data policy and the SDGs.

*Data Product
of Sustainable
Development
Science Satellite
1 (SDGSAT-1) by
CASEarth*

3 SELECT ISSUES RELATING TO THE CASEARTH DATA POLICY AND SUMMARY OF INTERVIEWS

According to China's data policy system, the scope and applicability of the CASEarth Data Policy is limited to the CAS program level. It is, therefore, different and separate from other national or institutional programs and their data policies.

There are a number of other ways, however, to characterize and analyze the issues of concern to policymakers regarding the CASEarth Program and to environmental observation data access and use generally. There are the diverse attitudes and practices of different nations and research communities on both the discipline (and even sub-discipline) and institutional levels. National cultural attitudes and values are also very important.

In the context of this review, it is useful to examine

several key issues of which CASEarth managers and the other readers of this report should be cognizant. We do not pretend this to be a comprehensive discussion. Rather, we have selected several key data policy topics that we believe are beneficial and important for the CASEarth Program to consider as it moves forward into its next phase under CBAS.

We have identified three general issue areas in this regard. First, is the incomplete and evolving nature of the laws governing the CASEarth research data. Second, is the inherent economic and legal nature of networked digital research data that affects policy formation to guide those activities. And, third, are the benefits and drawbacks of an open data policy.

3.1 THE INCOMPLETE AND EVOLVING NATURE OF THE LAWS GOVERNING CASEARTH RESEARCH DATA

Earth observation satellites and various sensor systems and the Big data they produce, particularly for research purposes, have not yet become the subject matter of an international convention or of a treaty-based organization, as noted earlier in the previous chapter. On the one hand, this could be a limiting factor in that a more legally binding, top-down set of rules to which governments have agreed do not guide the related activities at the national level. This can undermine certainty, especially in an inherently global activity. It is also a reflection of the relative newness of the technologies. Thus, there is not currently enough interest by and support of governments to produce a treaty-based organization or a more binding convention that codifies the emerging norms that we outlined above.

On the other hand, the lack of such more binding instruments and implementing organizations may be

viewed in a more positive light. Top-down laws and institutions may have greater effect but are necessarily watered down in their content and prescriptive guidance, particularly at the intergovernmental level. Governments are very cautious to form binding commitments and such multilateral mechanisms tend to be inflexible, cumbersome, and expensive to monitor and enforce. Moreover, although there is less directly relevant international law in this arena than in some other technologies and research activities, there are many organizations that have either been formed or have turned their attention in recent years to the data issues that are at the heart of Earth and environmental observations.

Indeed, attention to public-sector information and data as infrastructure, especially over the past decade, has never been greater and is certain to increase

for the foreseeable future as digital networks and technologies progress. The developments in recent years thus have been encouraging. The brief descriptions of the intergovernmental and non-governmental international organizations in the previous chapter paint a particularly positive picture in this regard. More binding commitments would be slower still and could (ironically) be less prescriptive. As more government officials and communities of practice in Earth

observations research internalize the arguments for the many benefits of openness as a default rule, as discussed further below, they may naturally come to support more forceful expressions toward that end. The framers of the CASEarth Program's Data Policy were clearly cognizant of the benefits such a policy would have for the research goals of the Program and this report seeks to reinforce that perspective.

3.2. ECONOMIC AND LEGAL CHARACTERISTICS OF DIGITAL RESEARCH DATA FOR DATA POLICY DEVELOPMENT

There are additional attributes of digital research data as an information product that need to be identified and briefly described and flagged for further potential data policy work. Some of these characteristics of research data are universal and should be taken into consideration in the changes to or development of data and research policy, whether at CASEarth or in other CAS research activities. Others are quite specific to the Chinese national or institutional context, which we cannot and do not try to describe. Advisory committees and experts within the CASEarth Program and its successor research activities may wish to follow-up on their implications in the future. In the remainder of this section, we examine some of the unique attributes of digital research data from broad economic, legal, and policy perspectives.

The threshold issue, and one that has been discussed many times over the last quarter century or so but nonetheless bears repeating, is the shift from the print (paper) paradigm to the digitally networked one. There are massive differences between the print and digitally networked paradigms, whether measured quantitatively or qualitatively. The quantitative differences are well known. Big Earth observational data have exploded in size and led to a new form of research—data science—over the past two decades and the CASEarth Program is a quintessential example of this trend.

From a qualitative, economic standpoint, several of the digitally networked characteristics particularly stand out. The limitless content creation and easy and immediate dissemination, together with the near-zero marginal distribution cost, make the digital paradigm potentially vastly more efficient, productive, and economically useful than the paper model.

Factual data from public funding, such as Earth and environmental observational data, have public good characteristics that make them ideally suited for their open availability and reuse on digital networks. “Public

goods” in economic terms have both non-depletable and non-rivalrous characteristics (Kaul et al., 2000). Unlike a physical private good, such as an orange, that will be appropriated and consumed the first time it is used, all digital information is, by definition, non-depletable since it cannot be exhausted by use. In fact, networked information gains in value the more that it is (re)used, a central tenet of the FAIR Data Principles.

Information, even in a digital form (i.e., data), can become rivalrous, however, in the sense that it can be fully protected and kept from use by others. Almost all public goods can be excluded from the user or cordoned off in some way. This means data is not a “pure” public good, which is why we designate it as a “quasi”-public good, although it is usually very inefficient to protect civil, non-profit observational data. It is especially inefficient in the case of publicly funded research data and information, not only because citizens have already paid for its production through taxes, but also because it gains in value from broad dissemination and reuse. Indeed, if the data are openly available on digital networks, there can be a “network effect” that may increase their value exponentially by the addition of many users who can then reuse the data in myriad and sometimes unanticipated ways, with others building on those results as well.

Openness as the default option is thus desirable because the activity that has created the data—a public government or academic research program—is itself also a public good, unless there are compelling reasons to keep the resulting data protected, as discussed further in this chapter. This argues in favor of keeping digitally networked, publicly funded Earth and environmental observational data and information as openly available and reusable as possible.

Moreover, from a legal perspective, data as such are factual observations of nature and not copyrightable under copyright law. When arranged in databases, the

database contents have a modicum of creativity and can be copyrighted (often referred to as “thin” copyright) or protected in some cases by database protection law in jurisdictions that have enacted such legislation (mostly in the E.U.). Data, and especially academic research data that may have little economic value as opposed to other types of value (e.g., scientific, educational, social), are thus anomalous legal subjects unlike more original and creative information products, such as books, articles, videos, and software, which can attract full copyright protection.

At the same time, private law sources include contracts (legally enforceable agreements between two or more parties) and licenses that are supported by public laws and that may be either more restrictive (End User

Licensing Agreements for commercial information products) or less restrictive (common-use licenses, such as those developed by Creative Commons) than the public statutes. Waivers of some or all intellectual property rights (placing the data and the dataset in the public domain) may also be expressed. In all cases, these are voluntary mechanisms that reflect the interests of the parties involved.

Public domain status enables the unrestricted reuse, re-dissemination, and legal interoperability of data unrestricted by intellectual property restrictions. Big data and big science programs, such as spatially referenced Earth and environmental observational data projects of CASEarth, will benefit the most from a free and open legal status, as we discuss in the next section.

3.3. THE BENEFITS AND DRAWBACKS OF AN OPEN DATA POLICY

The rapidly changing technological capabilities for creating, manipulating, disseminating, and using Earth observation data are giving rise to new issues and accentuating existing ones, as well as producing many new opportunities and challenges or making old ones even greater. The opportunities arise primarily in data-intensive research and applications that is global or international in scope, in the integration of heterogeneous data for new results, and in making vast amounts of factual information available for a broad spectrum of users for collaborative research and other potential uses. The inherent challenges and barriers pose competing interests to the principle of openness, sometimes legitimate and sometimes not, which must also be considered in effectively managing the data resources for optimal access and use, and for developing rational rules and structures for such processes.

There are well-known opportunities and benefits that are promoted by a policy that is based on openness to publicly funded data as the default rule. These include many research, educational, governance, and broad economic and social benefits. Because the CASEarth Program is a research activity, performed by a research organization, we begin with and emphasize the research and educational benefits. The economic, social, and governance benefits accrue mostly from verified and quality-controlled “operational” data derived from environmental monitoring programs, rather than new research projects. However, some of these ancillary benefits may be realized from research data as well, and the CASEarth Program makes available and uses data from operational systems, so some of these other perspectives may be relevant, too.

Many of the benefits identified here that the CASEarth Program should consider are taken from a report that CODATA prepared for the GEO Secretariat by one of the consultants involved in drafting the present review, so these issues are only briefly summarized here (CODATA 2015). These benefits remain valid and current, notwithstanding the seven years that have passed since that report was published. Additional details, as well as an extensive set of useful references pertaining to these issues, can be found in the 2015 CODATA document.

As we have already noted, networked digital information, especially public research data, have public good characteristics and strong potential network externalities that make them highly amenable and more productive under a policy of openness. More to the point, digital observational Earth and environmental data have additional qualities, such as the one-time possibility for observations of many natural phenomena, that make their broad disclosure and use even more beneficial (NRC 1999).

Indeed, many research and innovation opportunities increase with an open access and use data policy that adheres to the FAIR principles. To begin with, one of the key stated goals of the CASEarth Program, the promotion of international and interdisciplinary research in the furtherance of the SDGs can be greatly enhanced with more researchers being able to use the data. The permission extended to research data providers by the CASEarth Data Policy to its users to create new data products or data sets with the CASEarth data, with appropriate attribution, not only enables interoperability from a legal and policy perspective, but brings greater recognition to the Program, CAS, and

China for those uses and results. It allows the easier verification of previous research results by others, an important tenet in the scientific process. Data mining and the promotion of new kinds of research, including citizen science contributions, are made more possible. Moreover, another objective of the CASEarth Program, the education and training of new generations of researchers, particularly from LMICs, is promoted as well. In short, by reducing barriers to access and use, overall inefficiencies in the investments in the CASEarth Program, such as the duplication of the data acquisition and the research itself, can be eliminated, thereby pleasing both the direct funders of the Program and the nation generally.

There are further potential benefits from a policy of greater data openness that may not be central to the goals of the CASEarth Program and, therefore, do not currently appear in the CASEarth Data Policy but that should be mentioned as well. We already noted greater economic efficiency of such a policy, but as the 2015 CODATA report to GEO documents, it can support broader economic benefits and growth. The general social welfare can be enhanced. And, finally, there can be greater benefits of more effective governance and policy making, including improved decision making with the data, demonstrating more publicly CAS and China's leadership and broadening influence in the research community, building trust, and promoting capacity-building among LMIC researchers, all stated or at least implicit goals of the CASEarth Program and CAS.

In addition, in the February 22, 2022 online discussion, the CASEarth Review Team identified several other benefits that were considered in the development of the CASEarth Data Policy. They noted that:

As technology develops, it is becoming more and more important for researchers to be able to share and acquire scientific data in a timely manner. As more and more data are generated and shared, they must adopt effective data management practices. For this reason, we believe open data policy should be followed to maximize the value of scientific data. From our perspective, it may have the following benefits:

1. *Enhance data exchange and accuracy, as well as facilitate data normalization;*
2. *Facilitate data integration and promote knowledge sharing, as data can be made more valuable and easier to find;*
3. *Enhance the consistency and reusability of data, facilitate the acquisition, understanding, and reuse of data, contribute to knowledge discovery, and improve transparency of research;*

4. *Improve the integrity and influence of data and data research;*
5. *Extend the range of possible applications for data, facilitate collaboration; and*
6. *Promote the development of infrastructure and services to enable scientific practice to move to open scientific systems.*

Although there clearly are many reasons to implement a public Earth observation research data policy with a default rule of openness, there also are a number of compelling and legitimate reasons not to provide open availability to all data, all of the time, to all people. Such reasons include those of protecting a nation's security, law enforcement, and public safety; not compromising personal privacy; securing various forms of confidentiality and intellectual property rights; guarding the exclusive use of research data prior to publishing results; and restrictions for other cultural or religious reasons.

The CASEarth Review Team noted a number of other drawbacks related to the CASEarth Data Policy, including:

1. *Extra costs in terms of additional facilities, infrastructures, etc.;*
2. *Data ethics, privacy, security, and copyright issues, and the need to strike a balance between security and privacy [Note: these issues were covered above, but we have included them in order to be complete.];*
3. *Imperfections of standards, norms, and technologies related to open data;*
4. *Huge gap between formulation and implementation of open data policies; and*
5. *A good open culture and an effective incentive mechanism are required in the science community.*

3.4 SUMMARY FINDINGS FROM INTERVIEWS WITH STAKEHOLDERS INSIDE AND OUTSIDE OF CHINA¹¹

Through interviews with dozens of stakeholders, we were able to explore the broad range of experiences and perspectives of both China-based and foreign users of CASEarth data and the Data Sharing and Services Portal, and identify the corresponding strengths, weaknesses, opportunities, and threats to the Program's Data Policy and its various components. Below are the summary findings from those interviews. Conclusions and recommendations based on this input and the other analyses above are provided in Chapter 4.

3.4.1. Findings from interviews in China

This review has incorporated the opinions and suggestions of 31 scientists and researchers working in China who were interviewed by the CODATA Consultant Review Team. The interviewees included: 6 scientists of the CASEarth Program; 5 data providers and scientific publishers; 8 domestic users; 1 member of International Science Council's World Data System (ISC WDS); 3 technical data management experts; 2 members of the CASEarth data sharing working group; 5 platform developers; and 1 data management engineer. The comments from those interviewees covered both the development and implementation of the CASEarth Data Policy and the design and development of the CASEarth Data Sharing and Service Portal.

3.4.1.1. Strengths and opportunities

Based on the comments from domestic interviewees, we are able to identify the Program's strengths and opportunities. Strengths refer to positive internal factors that should be enhanced by the CASEarth Program/CBAS and their associated partners. It is the strengths of the CASEarth Program that lay the foundation for the future of those activities and allow it to take advantage of external opportunities to further increase its international prominence and advance its global influence.

The strengths and opportunities of the CASEarth Program as viewed by stakeholders inside China are summarized as follows:

- Holding a rich variety of data that covers a wide range of fields and disciplines
- Promoting the sharing of data, algorithms, and models
- CASEarth Data Policy may play an exemplary role for data quality and the timely management of data
- Utilizing satellite data from different sources (both domestic and abroad)
- Supported by the Big Earth Data journal to build a new reward system
- Enjoying national financial and institutional support that ensures the sustainability of the CASEarth Program
- Adopting the FAIR Data Principles to improve data use and value
- Raising public awareness of the importance of data sharing through a variety of reward systems
- Aiming to be the first open-data platform targeting SDGs
- Providing a unified platform for some of the global Big Earth Data
- Benefiting from the development of the Belt and Road Initiative
- Meeting the potential needs of developing countries

3.4.1.2. Weaknesses and threats

In parallel to the strengths and opportunities, we also identify the CASEarth Program's weaknesses and threats. In contrast to strengths, weaknesses refer to the negative internal factors that should be controlled and improved. Correspondingly, there are also some impediments or external limits that might be beyond the control of the CASEarth Program but could potentially threaten its long-term sustainability. The CASEarth Program/CBAS should actively improve the areas of key weaknesses while at the same time remain alert to potential future challenges.

¹¹ This section examines task statement "c. Appraise the extent to which the CASEarth Programme's mission of supporting scientific contributions to the SDGs through earth observations has been facilitated by its data policy and the supporting human and technical infrastructures. The review will consider whether the data policy enables activities such as education and training, data science and applications, the development of various science-ready open data products and other scientific and social objectives?" and part of Statement of Task "d. Develop conclusions...", from the perspective of knowledgeable experts within and external to China.

The key areas of future improvement are summarized as follows:

- Developing better program mechanisms for data collection and sharing
- Further clarification of legal and policy issues on data sharing
- Devoting more effort to encourage the utilization of domestic satellite data
- Continuously enhancing data sharing practices by strengthening CASEarth's adherence to all aspects of the FAIR Data Principles
- Further expansion of the geographical coverage of the Big Earth Data
- Reinforcing internal training and communication to facilitate the sharing of long-term visions among participating scientists and members
- Further improvement of the platform's visibility and prominence through international platforms
- Gaining more experience in managing infrastructure compared with other platforms
- Devoting more research efforts to data standards in areas where international references are absent
- Improving the culture of data sharing to ensure the long-term sustainability of the program
- Paying more attention to and more focus on the SDGs in global, regional, national, and local levels
- Problem-solving for SDG-oriented data integration, management, and services should be the priority for the CASEarth Data Policy system development

3.4.2. Findings from interviews outside of China

The 28 foreign user interviews included researchers, data users, and other individuals from across the globe. Of that group, 20 interviewees were recommended by CASEarth and 8 were identified and contacted by the CODATA Consultant Review Team. Overall, the interviewees were grouped in the following categories: 13 from Earth Sciences-related intergovernmental bodies; 5 from scientific bodies focused on Earth Sciences and SDG areas; 8 international researchers/users; 1 government agency official; and 1 publisher/editor from a scientific journal.

The responses to the survey fell largely into two distinct

groups: 1) users of CASEarth data and/or researchers with strong collaborations with Chinese scientists; and 2) individuals well-versed in Earth observation systems and Earth sciences who were generally unaware of the CASEarth data platform or CASEarth's overall resources and capabilities.

Most of the interviewees recommended by CASEarth were either: 1) not familiar with the CASEarth Data Policy or the Data Sharing and Service Portal; 2) or did not use the Portal, relying instead on acquiring data and data products through their direct collaborations with Chinese colleagues. Those most likely to be aware of the Portal were researchers directly involved in the Digital Belt and Road initiative. Most of the other foreign interviewees identified by the CODATA Consultant Review Team as heavily engaged in the Earth science data field were not aware of the Portal and, consequently, had not used it.

3.4.2.1. Strengths and opportunities

Based on the comments from interviewees outside of China, we are able to identify the Program's strengths and opportunities. Strengths here refer to positive internal factors that should be enhanced by the CASEarth Program/CBAS and their associated partners in developing further their data policy. It is the strengths that lay the foundation for the future of these activities and allow it to take advantage of external opportunities to further increase its international prominence and advance its global influence.

The strengths and opportunities of the Program as viewed by stakeholders outside China are summarized as follows:

- Broad support for CASEarth's efforts and intentions regarding data sharing
- Support for the web-based portal and platform
- CASEarth data are Findable and Accessible (FA of the FAIR Data Principles)¹²
- Potential for CASEarth to contribute significantly to the Sustainable Development Goals
- The advantages of increased visibility
- Improving the data policy and its implementation—for the long-term
- Providing more opportunities for LMIC users through the Digital Belt and Road initiative

¹² The topic of Interoperable and Reusable (the IR of FAIR) was not discussed with interviewees outside of China in sufficient detail to draw any firm conclusions regarding CASEarth's efforts in this area.

3.4.2.2. Weaknesses and threats

In addition to strengths and opportunities, we also identify the weaknesses of and threats to the CASEarth Program and its Data Policy. Weaknesses focus on the negative internal factors that should be better managed and improved. There also exist impediments or external factors beyond CASEarth's control but which could be potential threats to the long-term sustainability of the program. The CASEarth Program/CBAS should devote energy to improvements in key areas of weaknesses while also remaining vigilant to potential challenges in the future.

The key areas for future improvement of the CASEarth Program's Data Policy are summarized as follows:

- Need for greater publicity and communication regarding the data policy and its implementation
- Need for comparability between data available through Chinese and English websites
- Adherence to all the FAIR Data Principles in the CASEarth portal
- Lack of visibility of and access to cloud-based services
- Technical problems with the CASEarth website and ease of access to the Data Sharing and Services Portal
- Lack of visibility and awareness of CASEarth and its data portal at the international level could diminish the value of its investment
- Lack of a legal, clear, and simple data policy could impact long-term viability
- Limiting access to raw data diminishes potential global role
- Absence of a clear commitment to long-term sustainability could diminish use of the data portal and services by international users

*Moonlight Bay,
Kanas, Xinjiang,
China by CASEarth*

4 CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS REGARDING THE CASEARTH DATA POLICY

4.1. CONCLUSIONS

In the course of this review, it has become clear that the Chinese Academy of Sciences and the CASEarth Program consider the Program to be not only a “flagship” research initiative but are intent on establishing a successful open data policy based on generally accepted international norms. While the current policy provides a strong foundation, improvements to it should focus on issues of visibility, outreach, and compliance.

Since a data policy that is as open as possible and as closed as necessary is increasingly the norm in public international research, it is important to educate data users on the rationale underlying such a policy, and the benefits that the policy and adherence to it can bring. Equally important is the development of the skills and infrastructure necessary to implement the FAIR (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable) Data Principles which, in conjunction with the open data policy, will bring the greatest benefits through data (re) use. Conversely, it is essential to minimize the negative aspects of non-compliance in a realistic and useful manner. The Program could certainly improve and expand its education of data users in these areas.

The CASEarth platform now provides open access to rich varieties of data covering a wide range of fields and disciplines, including climate change, natural resources management, environmental conservation, and biodiversity and ecosystem studies. Not limited to scientific data sharing, CASEarth also allows the sharing of new algorithms and research models, with the ambitious goal of facilitating more complex cloud computing and online data analysis. However, data collection and publication in the CASEarth Program is inevitably constrained by bureaucratic challenges and some legal ambiguity. Further improvement is needed to comply with the FAIR Data Principles, especially the interoperability and reusability principles, to facilitate access to and reuse of CASEarth datasets and data products by internal and external users.

There are many institutions worldwide engaged in this type of Earth science research. The CASEarth subject-matter focus is, nonetheless, appropriate, particularly regarding the emphasis on the UN Sustainable Development Goals from a Big Earth and environmental data perspective, especially in the next phase of the Program. This is an area of critical importance in which few players are involved from a Big data standpoint. There also is room for improvement in the greater coordination of research objectives and data activities with other relevant groups, especially UN DESA, UNEP, UNCCD, UN-Habitat, UNBL, and FAO, as documented in Chapter 2, in order to take advantage of synergies, minimize redundancies, and maximize the utilization of CASEarth data—a key outcome of an effective data policy.

Compared with some conventional platforms run by foreign entities, this new platform in China stands out as the first to target the SDGs with some unique datasets and advanced algorithms to support decision-making in sustainable development. Domestically, the Program has received increasing support after China reaffirmed its commitment to the SDGs. Internationally, CASEarth not only benefits from China’s Belt and Road Initiative through strengthened local collaborations, but also holds the potential to provide Big data support to developing countries.

Nevertheless, due to its relatively short history, CASEarth’s methods of collecting, storing, sharing, and processing data will need continuous improvement even beyond the completion of the current Program. Building up data standardization systems for non-satellite data remains a complex problem that requires innovative solutions. Improved data categorization and data recommendation systems are necessary to ensure that the data can be quickly found by its potential users. The many possible benefits of combining various data sources are noted above (See Chapter 2 Section 2.1.)

Further, good communication between engineers/technicians and scientists is crucial to identify further potential applications of data resources, enriching metadata with more accurate attributes, adjusting data formats and grid sizes, and enhancing the interoperability between satellite and non-satellite data. Increasing the number of data management scientists could be one solution to solve the communication problems. These would be professionals who can work as brokers between engineers/technicians building the data sharing portal and scientists from specific fields. In addition, more efforts are required to improve the English version of the data platform and the data products to allow foreign users to find, access, and reuse these data.

From the individual user perspective, foreign interviewees who worked with Chinese collaborators were generally very positive in their comments and impressions of CASEarth and the Chinese data resources they were using. It was not always clear, however, whether the data sets being referenced had been obtained directly through the CASEarth platform or through direct collaborations with Chinese colleagues (although where this differentiation was articulated, most of the data had come through personal interactions, not the web platform). Many of the non-Chinese interviewees were either aware of CASEarth but had never tried to access its data resources or were unaware of the capacity that exists through CASEarth.

Among both groups, there was limited knowledge of the CASEarth Data Policy. Any familiarity was often

only the result of the CODATA Consultant Review Team having provided a translation of the policy prior to the interview. There were numerous calls for more active communication and dissemination on the part of CASEarth, especially in terms of making the data policy and other resources available in English, and for CASEarth to make a greater effort to raise its visibility in the international community. At the same time, CASEarth received high praise for its efforts and intention to make its data products open and accessible, even among those who were unfamiliar with CASEarth's capabilities.

Finally, the short courses for selected young researchers from Low-to-Middle Income Countries (LMICs), as well as online training modules, are primarily or exclusively focused on the scientific and technical aspects of research data and their use. The underlying rationale for a policy that emphasizes the FAIR Data Principles and the sharing and reuse of scientific data as much as possible is not being promoted. While researchers do not need to be data policy experts, they should understand that rationale and approach to be successful in their work, particularly in furthering the goals of the CASEarth Program, the SDGs, and generally being good citizens. We note the on-line 2022 International Training Workshop on Open Science and SDGs--co-sponsored by CBAS, CODATA, and others--as a prime example of the type of training opportunities that will be of great benefit to CASEarth/CBAS data users from LMICs and other regions of the world.

4.2. RECOMMENDATIONS

The recommendations below are all directed to the CASEarth Program managers to decide how best to implement them, unless more specific actors are named. Also, the time for implementation is noted either in the near term, which means as soon as practicable but not later than the end of the current CASEarth Program, or in the longer term, or CBAS, which will take over the infrastructure and continue to provide data services of CASEarth after its completion. The recommendations focus on both the CASEarth Data Policy and some programmatic aspects, as they are inextricably linked. Further development and implementation of the data policy and improvements in particular program elements are necessary to ensure its successful implementation.

4.2.1. Recommendations to improve the implementation and effectiveness of the CASEarth Program's research data policies

1. Based on the rationale presented throughout this study, we commend the CASEarth Program for adopting a default rule of openness for its data resources, subject only to legitimate and justified restrictions. The data policy should take advantage of and accentuate the positive underlying rationale and minimize the negative effects it might have. The areas that ought to be considered in developing the policy further are multidimensional and include technical, scientific, institutional, socio-cultural, economic, and legal considerations, as outlined throughout this report. The data policy should be reviewed internally from those perspectives prior to the launch of the next (CBAS) phase.

The CASEarth Program's Data Policy should encompass not only the open use of data and data products available through the Data Sharing and Services Portal (and its CBAS-based successor), but also the open aspects of data collection/submission, data analysis, and data processing by data providers and users outside of the CASEarth Program.

In addition, the CASEarth Program should work with other research projects and organizations across the Chinese government to standardize open data policies.

2. The CASEarth Program needs to publish its data policy (not just its data license) on its website, in both the Chinese and English versions, in order to promote visibility, transparency, and compliance.
3. Any changes made in the existing data policy need to be fully substantiated and justified so that there will be understanding and respect by those who need to subsequently implement and abide by it. Such changes should be made with the data user perspectives in mind.

Although there are some examples and anecdotal information that support the existing data policy, the CASEarth Program may wish to undertake several pilot projects to demonstrate to the public, policymakers, and funders the scientific, economic, social, and other effects of an open and FAIR data policy. As documented in this report, there are numerous previous studies that are good examples for how this can be done.

In this regard, the CASEarth Program should analyze various "use cases" both inside and outside China in order to improve its data sharing policy, including its privacy protections, in order to encourage a wider range of use of its data and data products, especially as applied to different disciplines, industries, and regions.

4. Because "ownership" of the data policy is important to improve its effectiveness and subsequent compliance, key representatives of major stakeholder groups be involved in the continuing development and implementation of the CASEarth Program's Data Policy. These representatives should come from the groups and institutions identified as the sources for interviewees for this report, as described in Chapter 1, Section 2.
5. Promoting compliance with the data policy should include a mix of incentives and penalties that are specifically targeted at the category of data providers and users in question.
6. In order to positively promote the data policy and its benefits, a selection of prizes and professional recognition should be implemented that each year reward the individuals, both within and external to China, who demonstrate the most creativity and productivity in using and disseminating the CASEarth Program's data for research and public interest uses.
7. The researcher or educator from outside of the government and business who uses any civil government Earth observation data, including CASEarth Program data, in a publication should deposit the data that underpin the results of the research in an open, public repository that is approved by CASEarth/CBAS, or at a minimum make such data available upon request after publication or within a specified period. To help enforce compliance with this recommendation, the researcher or educator must demonstrate that the supporting data were made available. The CASEarth Program and/or CAS itself, which funds the research, should investigate any reports of non-compliance from third parties and take appropriate disciplinary action, up to and including the withholding of further research funds.
8. We also commend the CASEarth Program for further focusing its research goals on the SDGs, thereby making the results of the research more socially and internationally useful and relevant. In the longer term, from an environmental data policy perspective, we were encouraged to learn that the CBAS will be funded through at least 2030. The SDG projects extend to the end of this decade and no doubt beyond. If the SDGs are extended beyond 2030, then CBAS should be extended as well.
9. Because environmental observational data increase in value the longer that they are collected, ideally in a consistent manner, they are useful for documenting long-term changes to the environment. The data collected under the Program's auspices, therefore, should not only be preserved, including sufficient backup, and continue to be made openly available as much as possible, but that the research results, infrastructure, and data policy should be closely coordinated with and used as appropriate for any follow-on research to make sure that the investments in the existing CASEarth Program are fully utilized.
10. The CASEarth Program and then the CBAS should review its activities from a duplication of effort and coordination perspective on an annual basis, both in China and internationally.

4.2.2. Recommendations to ensure greater benefit to users of CASEarth data resources

1. The CASEarth Program should place more emphasis on providing data products, rather than raw data, that could support decision-making related to the UN SDGs. While we recognize that there exist different preferences among researchers, we believe that providing more data products concerned with the SDGs will help distinguish the CASEarth Data Sharing and Service Portal from other international data providers and increase the prominence of the CASEarth and CBAS. This is also practical given the fact that the CASEarth Program does not own many satellite and non-satellite data administered by different government institutions and agencies. The direct sharing of raw data (especially fine-grained satellite data and sensitive socio-economic statistical data) may cause concerns over intellectual property and privacy rights and adequate protection of national security.

Further, the Program should continuously explore the potential broad value of its data products not only for academic communities but also for governmental and non-governmental institutions. It is essential for the Program to have some flagship data products that can support cutting-edge research and policymaking related to the SDGs. These flagship data products would help attract more domestic and foreign users, increase the dissemination and use of CASEarth Program data, and heighten the international reputation of the CASEarth and CBAS.

2. The CASEarth Program should continue to improve the interoperability of its datasets, especially between satellite and non-satellite data. The Program ought to integrate data from multiple sources, rather than focusing only on remote sensing data with non-satellite data playing a complementary role. Non-satellite data usually require georeferencing to integrate with satellite data. Though there is a large amount of socioeconomic census data shared through the Big Earth Data platform, limited georeferencing work has impeded the unification of satellite and non-satellite data. Furthermore, the current categorization of the data based on sub-projects may also hinder the integration of data. This situation might be improved with the re-categorization of the data according to the SDGs.

3. Further enrichment and better scrutiny of metadata will be crucial to strengthen the reusability of the Big Earth Data. The CASEarth Program has devoted substantial effort to control data quality through external reviews. However, there are still concerns with inconsistent review standards. Furthermore, to make the data reusable, the metadata should be richly described with a plurality of accurate and relevant attributes. Current metadata systems are designed in a rather simple way to accommodate a wide range of data and that some data released by CASEarth have metadata with unclear or limited explanations. Some scientists (such as biologists) find the problem of underdeveloped metadata systems more salient than others. Therefore, CASEarth also should develop more detailed and discipline-specific metadata specifications, including object description, date and time when the data was collected, and data collection method description, especially for raw data. Having a time stamp on data with the latest updated information also would be very useful.

4. The CASEarth Program should enhance the English version of the data sharing platform and materials available within it to strengthen the implementation and effectiveness of the Program's data policy. Limited English translation constrains the capacity of foreign users to find and access scientific data provided by the CASEarth's Data Sharing and Service Portal. The sub-projects under the CASEarth umbrella lack both funding and people to develop English translations of the (meta) data. Sometimes there are no English translations. Sometimes the translations differ greatly from the Chinese version. This situation directly impacts the ability of CASEarth to successfully implement its data policy. Increasing the number of data management scientists could be one solution to solve the communication problems. These would be professionals who can work as brokers between engineers/technicians building the portal and scientists from specific fields.

From the February 22 and March 1, 2022 workshops with the CASEarth Review Team, we understand that, under CBAS, automatic machine translation will be verified and adopted, and scientists will be encouraged to submit their data with English translations. However, specialized funding for enhancing the English version of the platform and metadata probably should be allocated, in part to provide for quality checks of translations. Only when the English version of the platform becomes available to users can the CASEarth Program achieve its full potential and prominence.

5. The CASEarth Program should continue to refine and improve the data access portal through additional actions, including: increasing the amount of data and information being made available; increasing the depth and breadth of data available in specific scientific areas; expanding the availability of data and data products relating to areas outside of China; and making the Data Sharing and Service Portal registration process as simple as possible.
6. Policymakers and funders must ensure the long-term viability/sustainability of the CASEarth Program/CBAS and its data resources. The full value of the CASEarth Program hinges on its sustainability. After the completion of the CASEarth Program in 2022, the responsibilities of long-term maintenance of the Big Earth data will be taken over by CBAS. It is important for decision makers to realize that the maintenance of infrastructure, data, and human resources might require no less financial and human investment than the initial build-up, and that the maintenance of infrastructure and hardware cannot be separated from the maintenance of a talented team.

Moreover, the continued success of the Program rests on the continued development of an open data culture in China. Under current academic award systems, which give more weight to scientific papers than data, scientists who share scientific data only may receive limited academic recognition. To change the current reward system and a better balance between scientific papers and data, improved incentive mechanisms are needed, including recording and publicizing data citations, carrying out periodical citation reviews, launching scientific data journals, and tracking the use of data products by policy and decisions makers. Some approaches have already been adopted by the CASEarth Program and its sub-projects. A comprehensive post-Program evaluation of these approaches will provide clues to the further advance of open science and open data after the CASEarth Program concludes.
7. CASEarth managers need to address technical issues regarding CASEarth webpages and links between the CASEarth homepage and the Data Portal and Service website, including: repairing broken links; and fixing information on webpages displayed from dropdown menus.
8. CASEarth managers need to increase the visibility and utilization of the CBAS/CASEarth Data Sharing and Service Portal (including cloud services) by: 1) participating in international symposia and conferences as attendees and presenters, and through sponsorship of display booths and other publicly accessible activities at appropriate meetings; and 2) increasing partnerships with international data organizations, such as the Group on Earth Observations, outside the United Nations system. In this regard, we were heartened to learn about the Program's cooperation within the UN, especially with UN DESA, UNEP, UNCCD, UN-Habitat, UNBL, and FAO, as documented in Chapter 2.

4.3. CONCLUDING OBSERVATIONS

The Big Earth Data Science Engineering Program of Chinese Academy of Sciences (CASEarth) is a well-structured, well-funded research activity that is perhaps the most prominent research program now at CAS. By revising its focus to the United Nations Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) during the course of this review, the Program has sought to achieve global international prominence and relevance that will carry it forward through the International Research Center of Big Data for Sustainable Development, or CBAS. It, therefore, promises to assume a leadership role in Chinese and international research on the SDGs using Big data.

A major part of that leadership and prominence can be

attributed to the Program's open data policy and the free, online availability of many of its data holdings. These networked data have both classic public-good characteristics and support the highly important public-interest objectives that are embodied in the SDGs themselves, particularly for the Low-to-Middle-Income Countries (LMICs).

This review report is intended to strengthen the CASEarth Data Policy and, accordingly, the impact of the Program for the SDGs, the international research community, and CAS itself. It is our hope that the suggestions presented here will help improve the Program to achieve its desired full potential.

*Kanas Lake,
Xinjiang, China,
China by CASEarth*

5 ANNEXES

5.1. THE CODATA CONSULTANT REVIEW TEAM AND THE CASEARTH REVIEW TEAM

5.1.1. The CODATA Consultant Review Team

Paul F. UHLIR: Paul is an independent consultant in information policy and management. He was Scholar at the National Academy of Sciences (NAS) in Washington, DC in 2015-2016, and both founder and Director of the Board on Research Data and Information at the NAS, 2008-2015. Paul was employed at the NAS from 1985-2015, first as a senior staff officer for the Space Studies Board, where he worked on solar system exploration and environmental remote sensing studies for NASA, and then as associate executive director of the Commission on Physical Sciences, Mathematics, and Applications. He directed the Office of International S&T Information for eight years after that, where he organized projects and meetings on scientific data throughout the world, and from 1992 to 2015 he also was director of the US CODATA at the NAS. Before joining the NAS, he worked in the general counsel's office at the National Oceanic and Atmospheric Administration of the Department of Commerce in Washington, DC. Paul has a B.A. degree in world history from the University of Oregon (1977), and a Master's degree in foreign relations and a Juris Doctor degree from the University of San Diego (1984, 1983). For more detailed information about his professional activities, see his website at: www.paulfuhlir.com. Paul was a lead consultant on this review, responsible for much of the writing of the report and integration of the text.

Robert SAMORS: Robert is an independent consultant on open/FAIR data policy analysis, development, and strategic implementation. He currently serves as the Senior Scholar for the Association of American Universities' Accelerating Public Access to Research Data (APARD) Initiative. Previously, he worked for the Belmont Forum as the Coordination Officer for the e-Infrastructures & Data Management (e-I&DM) Project managing the development of the Forum's data sharing principles and best practices, effective data planning and stewardship among grantees, and data sharing training curricula. Before that he worked for the

Group on Earth Observations (GEO) as Senior External Relations Manager designing and implementing GEO's external engagement strategy. Earlier positions have included: Associate Vice President for Innovation and Technology Policy at the Association of Public and Land-grant Universities (APLU); Associate Vice President for Federal Relations for the University of North Carolina System; and Assistant Vice President for Research at the University of Michigan. He holds a Master's in Public Policy from the Harvard University Kennedy School of Government, and a B.A. in Economics from Brown University. He is a member of the American Geophysical Union's Data Advisory Board. Robert was the other lead consultant on this review, responsible for research, analysis and production of report, English language interviews, and summary.

Aitong LI (see https://www.researchgate.net/profile/Aitong_Li): Dr. LI has a postdoctoral appointment at the Department of Geography and Resource Management, The Chinese University of Hong Kong, Hong Kong, and at the Graduate School of Public Policy, The University of Tokyo, Japan. She has degrees from Peking University, Yale University, and the University of Tokyo and speaks fluent Mandarin, Japanese, and English. She focuses on environmental sustainability policy. She provided research on the Chinese language information of the CASEarth programme, interviewed experts in China, and summarized the results.

Simon HODSON (see <http://www.codata.org/about-codata/secretariat>): Dr. Hodson is Executive Director of CODATA in Paris, France, and an expert in research data management and policy. He chaired the European Commission's Expert Group on FAIR Data which produced the report Turning FAIR into Reality. He was the vice-chair of the UNESCO Open Science Advisory Committee, tasked with drafting the UNESCO Recommendation on Open Science, which was adopted in 2021. He was responsible for the primary editorial oversight and for project management and logistics of this review.

5.1.2. The CASEarth Review Team

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Gensuo JIA: PhD, Research Professor at the Institute of Atmospheric Physics, CAS, Director of East Asian Regional Centre of Global Change Research, and Leader of the planning working group for the CASEarth Program. His research interests focus on Earth observation of global change, and ecosystem and climate interaction.

Wanrong WU: MS, Assistant of CASEarth Program, responsible for assisting the review project in related activities, dealing with gathering and sorting documentation, keeping in touch with the CODATA Consultant Review Team, paying attention to the review progress, and ensuring smooth operation of the review.

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DBAR Big Earth Data System <http://www.opendbar.cn/#/index>

5.3. KEY DOCUMENTS

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FAIR Data Principles <https://www.nature.com/articles/sdata201618?ref=https://githubhelp.com>

5.3.1. CASEarth Data Sharing Policy

Note: we have reproduced below sections 3.1 and 3.2 of the “Blue Book” (Guo et al., 2019), which we consider to have the key elements of the CASEarth Data Policy. All of Chapter 3 of the Blue Book report was recommended to us by the CASEarth Review Team as setting forth the data policy, and they provided a translated English version of that chapter.

CHAPTER THREE

Data Sharing System of Big Earth Data Science Engineering Project (CASEarth)

As resource development status and future construction plan are clarified, data sharing system of CASEarth, confronted with demands of scientific research innovation and multidisciplinary integration in the Big data era, follows the opening and sharing tide of international scientific data and the latest policies and measures shared by national data. The following aspects are focused: Firstly, principles and modes for data resource management and sharing services for CASEarth should be formed, and collection

mechanisms and opening and sharing policies and measures of data and products for CASEarth should be formulated to ensure the sustainable production of data resources and high-quality data resource gathering. Secondly, supervision, inspection and evaluation mechanisms of data sharing for CASEarth should be set up, and reviewable evaluation system and incentive measures should be built to realize the long-term and sustainable data resource opening and sharing. Lastly, infrastructure of data opening and sharing for CASEarth should be enhanced, and technical platforms and service capability should be improved to cultivate stable professional talent teams.

3.1 BASIC PRINCIPLES OF DATA OPENING AND SHARING

Data sharing for CASEarth will follow the principles of opening, unified responsibility, rights and interests, availability, sustainability and driving innovation, as shown in Table 3.1 in detail.

Table 3.1 Basic principles of data opening and sharing of CASEarth

Basic principle	Details
1. Principle of opening	Except the data whose opening and sharing are limited or forbidden by particular national laws and regulations, scientific data produced from CASEarth should be opened and shared without preconditions. Anyone, any legal entity and institution cannot regard data as private resources.
2. Principle of unified responsibility, rights and interests	The responsibility, rights and interests of data supervisor, data users and data providers should be clarified to form the interest coordination mechanisms that promote data sharing and build the sound data sharing ecology. Data users should make the data reference clear while publishing the scientific research achievements, and data providers should guarantee the quality of data.
3. Principle of availability	Responsible units and persons of CASEarth, subjects and subsidiary subjects should collect and process all kinds of scientific data based on the requirements of one source for one datum, mark on each datum and dynamic updating. They also should establish and update metadata information on schedule to ensure the authenticity, accuracy and effectiveness of shared data. Besides, data's discoverability, accessibility, interoperability, reusability and quotability should be guaranteed.
4. Principle of sustainability	Long-term acquisition mechanisms of scientific data for CASEarth should be built to guarantee software and hardware facilities and special teams needed in management and operation of scientific data and develop technology supporting system of scientific data management, opening and sharing. The sustainability of scientific data opening and sharing for CASEarth should be ensured through continuous guidance of policies, promotion of incentive mechanisms and dual support of technology and facilities.
5. Principle of driving innovation	Big data has brought revolutionary change to the way of scientific research. The way of scientists to know the nature and acquire the scientific discovery has been developed from traditional observation stage, experiment stage and model stage into the current Big data scientific discovery stage. Scientific research innovation driven by Big data and scientific discovery can be continuously promoted through data opening and sharing.

3.2 DATA SHARING POLICIES AND GUARANTEE MECHANISMS

3.2.1 Organization guarantee

A data sharing working group should be set up, and relevant work of data sharing for CASEarth should be organized and implemented under the leadership of an overall working group.

3.2.2 System guarantee

Management Measures of Data Sharing for CASEarth was issued, in which there are explicit classification systems of scientific data for CASEarth and ways of scientific data collection, management and storage, sharing (Department of Basic Research, Ministry of Science and Technology, 2014), and usage, as well as rights, interests and obligations of data producers, users and managers, to offer support to scientific data management and sharing for CASEarth.

3.2.3 Responsibility implementation

Data Sharing Plan should be formulated at the application stage of projects, subjects and subsidiary subjects. The undertakers of CASEarth tasks at various levels should separately elaborate the specific solutions of data sharing in implement solutions or plans according to related items of *Data Sharing Plan* at the stage of formulating implement solutions or signing plans.

The legal representatives of the legal entities where the undertakers of CASEarth tasks at various levels are located should write comments and sign their name on the *Data Sharing Plan*, and implement solutions or plans.

The institutions which intend to receive, manage and release shared data should write comments and sign their name on plans or implement solutions, promise to receive data in required quantity on time and provide the data sharing services in agreed forms on schedule with quality and quantity guaranteed.

3.2.4 Supervision and evaluation mechanisms

Data sharing supervision and evaluation mechanisms should be established for the whole process from project evaluation, process check to acceptance and assessment of projects, subjects and subsidiary subjects. At the application stage of projects, the content of *Data Sharing Plan* of projects, subjects and subsidiary subjects should be examined and approved by CASEarth according

to target and result output. The implementation of *Data Sharing Plan* should be examined and approved by CASEarth while signing implement solutions or plans. During the execution of CASEarth, data sharing in projects, subjects and subsidiary subjects should be dynamically evaluated by CASEarth regularly on schedule according to the content of implement plans, plans and *Metadata Specification*.

3.2.5 Incentive mechanisms

Data sharing evaluation system should be improved, and data sharing indicator should be set to carry out the regular examination and evaluation. Data sharing awarding policies should be implemented to offer awarding subsidies based on performance evaluation results. Cost of result sharing should be covered through cost compensation to motivate researchers to engage in activities including data acquiring, storage, opening and spreading. Intellectual property right and privacy of data should be protected to meet project groups' demands for prior use of data. Units and researchers participating in CASEarth should be encouraged to share scientific data produced from other scientific research projects through its platform, and other institutions in Chinese Academy of Sciences should be encouraged to positively share geoscientific data.

3.2.6 Long-term service mechanisms

Specialized institutions for CASEarth data sharing should be established, including unified operation and management organizations and network data nodes on data sharing platforms. Operation and management organizations are responsible for building and operating of sharing platforms, and network data nodes are responsible for data management, operation and maintenance. Software and hardware facilities and personnel teams needed in management and operation of scientific data should be guaranteed. Management system conforming to relevant standards and specifications and confidentiality and security requirements should be built and regularly updated and maintained to realize the safekeeping and sharing of scientific data. The cooperation and integration with international and domestic famous databases should be strengthened to further increase the availability of data. The sustainability of scientific data opening and sharing should be ensured in terms of human, financial and material resources, mechanisms and systems.

3.2.7 Data standard and specification development

Standards and specifications are the basis of standardized management, interconnectivity and opening and sharing of scientific data, where management of full life cycle from production, processing, storage, sharing to publishing and citing of scientific data is included. The scientific data production units should continuously compile, execute and implement the relevant standards and specifications of scientific data (databases) and data sharing technology for CASEarth, and construct complete standard systems. Meanwhile, relevant specifications of data sharing platform building, operation and maintenance should be set. The standardized work process including collection, management, services, sharing and evaluation of scientific data should be formulated, and generic technology supporting scientific data managing, opening and sharing services should be developed to

form the sound service ecology and ensure the effective connection and efficient services of scientific data resources of various subjects and sharing platforms.

3.2.8 Data publishing and citing encouragement

The publication of data for CASEarth should be further strengthened (Zhang X Q, Li X, 2015). So, publication and public citation of scientific data should be arranged and encouraged in CASEarth and the systems of Chinese Academy of Sciences, with special permanent process identifier (PID) set for data and data sharing and citation as important indicators in result evaluation. A new data citing index is proposed to be set, which equals to the number of citations of published datasets and impact factor weight of cited articles, becoming the crucial indicator to evaluate the effects of data sharing and influence of data.

5.4 INTERVIEW QUESTIONS

CASEarth Data Policy (or practice) interview questions:

The CAS Big Earth Data Science Engineering Program (CASEarth) has studied, since 2018, six SDGs: SDG 2 (Zero Hunger), SDG 6 (Clean Water and Sanitation), SDG 11 (Sustainable Cities and Communities), SDG 13 (Climate Action), SDG 14 (Life below Water), and SDG 15 (Life on Land).

1. Does your work focus on any of these six SDGs or other areas?
2. If yes, which SDGs and/or other areas?
3. To what degree has data made available through the CASEarth platform been helpful to your work in SDG XX (ask for each SDG referenced) or in other areas (ask for each specific area(s))?
A. Not Helpful **B.** Somewhat Helpful
C. Very Helpful
- 3.1 Please describe an experience where CASEarth's data sharing processes has been helpful in your work, whether for SDGs or other in other areas.
- 3.2 Please describe how CASEarth could improve its data sharing processes as they relate to your work, whether for SDGs or in other areas.

4. Is CASEarth open to receiving input from users and other stakeholders?

A. Yes **B.** No **C.** I Don't Know

- 4.1 How could CASEarth improve its data sharing policy and the implementation of that policy?

5. To what degree does CASEarth's Data Policy adhere to the "FAIR" principles for data stewardship (see <https://doi.org/10.1038/sdata.2016.18>)?

Findable:

A. Data are not Findable **B.** It requires considerable effort to Find data **C.** Data are easy to Find

Accessible:

A. Data are not Accessible **B.** It requires considerable effort to Access data
C. Data are easy to Access

Interoperable:

A. Data are not Interoperable
B. Data can be made Interoperable with some effort.
C. Data are Interoperable immediately

Reusable:

A. Data are not Reusable
B. Data can be made Reusable with some effort.
C. Data are Reusable immediately

6. CASEarth states that it is committed to data sharing. On a scale of 1-4 (1 = Poor and 4 = Excellent) how would you rate CASEarth's efforts to share data?
1. Poor 2. Adequate 3. Good 4. Excellent
- 6.1 Please provide some description or example of this conclusion about the sharing of CASEarth data.
7. CASEarth is striving to provide Big Earth Data sharing and cloud-based online analysis features at the international, regional and national levels. How would you rate CASEarth's achievement of those objectives?
- Regional level**
A. No progress B. Some progress C. Has achieved objectives D. Has exceeded objectives
- National level**
A. No progress B. Some progress C. Has achieved objectives D. Has exceeded objectives
- International level**
A. No progress B. Some progress C. Has achieved objectives D. Has exceeded objectives
8. In 2018, the government of China issued a regulation (data policy) regarding Scientific Data Management Measures (see http://www.gov.cn/zhengce/content/2018-04/02/content_5279272.htm for the text of the regulations). To what extent do you feel that CASEarth has implemented the data policy in the following areas:
- 8.1 Established rules and regulations while implementing national scientific data policies.
A. Not at all B. Has made some progress
C. Has implemented regulation D. Do not know
- 8.2 If data produced in government-funded research are used to write papers and for publication in foreign academic journals, they should be reported to related scientific data centers before being published.
A. Not at all B. Has made some progress C. Has implemented regulation D. Do not know
- 8.3 Data produced through government funding should be open to the public, except that which involves state secrets, national security, the public interest, commercial secrets and individual privacy.
A. Not at all B. Has made some progress
C. Has implemented regulation D. Do not know
9. Is information about CASEarth's Data Policy easy to obtain?
A. Yes B. No C. I don't know
- 9.1 If "No" or "I Don't Know", do you have any suggestions on how CASEarth could improve in this area?
- 9.2 Are there sufficient education and training opportunities for CASEarth data management and policy issues?
10. How does CASEarth's data sharing policy and implementation compare to other data providers?
A. Worse B. About the Same C. Better
- 10.1 Are there other organizations you would recommend as exemplars in data sharing whose policies and practices CASEarth could adopt?
11. Are there any other comments or issues you would like to raise that we have not covered?

5.5. CONVENTIONS USED IN THIS REPORT AND DEFINITIONS OF KEY TERMS

Throughout this document we use capitalization of several terms to indicate a specific definition or meaning. We shorten and capitalize the Chinese Academy of Sciences Big Earth Data Science Engineering Program as the CASEarth Program. The independent CODATA reviewers of the CASEarth Program's Data Policy who wrote and produced this report—Robert Samors, Paul Uhler, Aitong LI, and Simon Hodson—are referred to as the "CODATA Consultant Review Team." The internal CASEarth Program experts, listed and described in Annex 5.1, who were assigned to work with the CODATA Consultant Review Team are referred to as the CASEarth Review Team. The family names of all participants in the

review report, including the Chinese ones, are written second, after the first given names, consistent with the custom in the U.S and E.U. Grammatical conventions and style are presented in U.S. English, except in quoted text.

Literal quotes are either enclosed in "quotation marks" in running text or formatted in italics, if comprising one or more paragraphs. Where not explicitly noted, URLs were visited in the timeframe of February 2021 to August 2022. Generally, we provide URLs in footnotes, except where the composition of the URL, e.g., the parameterization, adds insight.

We also find it important to define several terms for a number of compelling reasons. Perhaps most obvious is that it is the first request (a) in the Statement of Task. Importantly, many of the readers of this report are Chinese, with English as their second language, so defining key concepts used throughout the manuscript is a useful reference point for our main audience. It also will help in the translation of the text. Related to this first point is that the scope of the review is international, so other potential readers also may not be native English speakers.

Many of the terms used throughout this report and its principal subject matter of research data policy and open data/open science are esoteric concepts and many are relatively new, as well. There are some potential readers who either may not be familiar with some of the terminology or may have different interpretations of what a term means. Finally, it is simply good practice to define key terms that are used in the report at the outset.

For all these reasons, we provide the following terms and their definitions below. Some of these terms are defined or explored further in the body of this manuscript. Rather than defining them ourselves, we use direct quotes from well-recognized and reputable sources that we consider relevant for the present purposes. Most of the definitions are directly quoted from the CASRAI Research Data Management Glossary (revised and reissued in August 2022 as the CODATA Research Data Management Terminology)¹³. Any other sources used are directly identified in individual terms. They have been arranged in alphabetical order, not in order of potential importance. We recognize that these are just one definition of many.

Big data: An evolving term that describes any voluminous amount of structured, semi-structured and unstructured data that have the potential to be mined for information.

Copyright: The United Nations World Intellectual Property Organization (WIPO) defines “copyright” as follows: Copyright (or author’s right) is a legal term used to describe the rights that creators have over their literary and artistic works. Works covered by copyright range from books, music, paintings, sculpture, and films, to computer programs, databases, advertisements, maps, and technical drawings. (<https://www.wipo.int/copyright/en/>)

Data: Facts, measurements, recordings, records, or observations about the world collected by scientists and others, with a minimum of contextual interpretation.

Database: A collection of data that is organized according to a conceptual structure/model describing the characteristics of these data and the relationships among their corresponding entities, supporting one or more application areas. A database allows its contents to be easily accessed, managed, and updated. The type of database used depends on the requirements of the study. A common type is the relational database, where data are related to each other in a systematic manner so that they can be reorganized and accessed in a number of different ways. A database may house one or many datasets.

Dataset: Any organized collection of data in a computational format, defined by a theme or category that reflects what is being measured/observed/monitored. The presentation of the data in the application is enabled through metadata.

Data policy: An organization’s stated data/information management processes designed to assist and protect the organization’s data research assets. It is a set of high-level principles that establish a guiding framework for data management. A data policy can be used to address strategic aspects such as data access, relevant legal matters, data stewardship issues and custodial duties, data acquisition and other issues.

Data sharing: The practice of making data available for reuse. This may be done, for example, by depositing the data in a repository, through data publication. SYNONYMS. Data dissemination; Data posting.

Information: The aggregation of data to make coherent observations about the world, meaningful data, or data arranged or interpreted in a way to provide meaning.

Intellectual property: WIPO defines “intellectual property” as follows: Intellectual property (IP) refers to creations of the mind, such as inventions; literary and artistic works; designs; and symbols, names and images used in commerce. IP is protected in law by, for example, patents, copyright and trademarks, which enable people to earn recognition or financial benefit from what they invent or create. By striking the right balance between the interests of innovators and the wider public interest, the IP system aims to foster an environment in which creativity and innovation can flourish. (<https://www.wipo.int/about-ip/en/>)

13 CASRAI (the Consortia Advancing Standards in Research Administration Information) has ended as an organization. The CASRAI glossary was moved to the CODATA website at: <https://codata.org/initiatives/data-science-and-stewardship/rdm-terminology-wg/> and a substantially revised product was released for public review in August 2022, as the CODATA Research Data Management Terminology.

Interoperability: The capability to communicate, execute programs, or transfer data among various functional units in a useful and meaningful manner that requires the user to have little or no knowledge of the unique characteristics of those units. Foundational, syntactic, and semantic interoperability are the three necessary aspects of interoperability.

Metadata: Literally, “data about data”; data that defines and describes the characteristics of other data, used to improve both business and technical understanding of data and data-related processes. Business metadata includes the names and business definitions of subject areas, entities and attributes, attribute data types and other attribute properties, range descriptions, valid domain values and their definitions. Technical metadata includes physical database table and column names, column properties, and the properties of other database objects, including how data is stored. Process metadata is data that defines and describes the characteristics of other system elements (processes, business rules, programs, jobs, tools, etc.). Data stewardship metadata is data about data stewards, stewardship processes and responsibility assignments.

Open data: Structured data that are accessible, machine-readable, usable, intelligible, and freely shared. Open data can be freely used, re-used, built on, and redistributed by anyone - subject only, at most, to the requirement to attribute and share-alike.

Open science: OECD defines “open science” as follows: Open science encompasses unhindered access to scientific articles, access to data from public research, and collaborative research enabled by ICT tools and incentives. Broadening access to scientific publications and data is at the heart of open science, so that research

outputs are in the hands of as many as possible, and potential benefits are spread as widely as possible. (<https://www.oecd.org/sti/inno/open-science.htm>)

Raw data: Data that exists in the form in which it was initially collected. It has not been processed for meaningful use. Although raw data have the potential to become “information,” they require selective extraction, organization, and sometimes analysis and formatting for presentation. As a result of processing, raw data sometimes end up in a database, which enables the data to become accessible for further processing and analysis in a number of different ways.

Research data: Data that are created by or used as primary sources to support technical or scientific enquiry, research, scholarship, or artistic activity, and that are used as evidence in the research process and/or are commonly accepted in the research community as necessary to validate research findings and results. All other digital and non-digital content have the potential of becoming research data. Research data may be experimental data, observational data, operational data, third party data, public sector data, monitoring data, processed data, or repurposed data.

Reuse (or re-use): Use of data or content outside of its original application or intention.

SWOT: A mnemonic acronym (Strengths, Weaknesses, Opportunities and Threats) used in structured planning.

Stakeholder: Individuals, groups or organizations that have an interest or share in an undertaking or relationship and its outcome - they may be affected by it, impact or influence it, and in some way be accountable for it.

5.6 REVIEWERS OF THIS REPORT

The following individuals conducted an independent external review of this report in June 2022. We list only their name and country of citizenship since they did not conduct this review as part of their official work duties. Rather, they were selected for this review based on their expertise and diversity of background. All family names are capitalized and the reviewers are listed in alphabetical order:

Bonnie C. CARROLL, United States

Wenbo CHU, China

Susan L. CUTTER, United States

Philippe DESMETH, Belgium

Bapon (Shm) FAKHRUDDIN, New Zealand

Natarajan ISHWARAN, France

Liqiang JI, China

Chuang LIU, China

Liangyun LIU, China

Hussein SHERIEF, Sudan

The report was also reviewed by the CODATA Executive Committee in August 2022.

*Chaka Salt Lake,
Gansu, Qinghai,
China by CASEarth*

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